

CATHOLICS AND POLITICS
IN NEW SOUTH WALES IN THE 1840s
WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO THE
LAND CONTROVERSY OF 1844

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A NOTE ON THE NEWSPAPERS

The Australasian Chronicle was first published by W.A. Duncan on 29 August 1839, became *The Morning Chronicle* on 11 October 1843, and *The Sydney Chronicle* on 11 July 1846. Abbreviations are respectively *AC*, *MC* and *SC*.

Duncan was editor until February 1843, Father John McEncroe until October 1843, and Michael D'Arcy until March 1847, when E.J. Hawkesley became editor. It appeared during most of its life twice weekly.

Duncan's second paper, *The Weekly Register of Politics, Facts and General Literature*, edited by W.A. Duncan, appeared weekly from 29 July 1843 until 27 December 1845. It is abbreviated *WR*.

[1]

INTRODUCTION

The 1840s were a time of profound change for New South Wales. The end of transportation, the rapid growth of the free population, the beginning of representative government, the formation of new political alliances, the end of the boom of the late 1830s in a depression of considerable severity, and an increase in working-class political activity were some of the factors making for change.

For the Catholic Church in the colony, the decade was also one of change, and of consolidation. By 1840 Catholics had gained a bishop, favourable Church and Education Acts, an increase of clergy, the first nuns, a newspaper, an influx of Irish immigrants, and a new confidence about their place in society, without, however, losing the disposition to consider themselves the victims of the intolerant, the haughty and the powerful.¹

The 1840s also saw begin in earnest the political conflict between pastoralists and the majority of the population which was to be ‘the most decisive factor in Australian politics in the nineteenth century’, a conflict which was not only a struggle for possession of the land, but which involved fundamentally opposed conceptions of the kind of society that could and should be developed [2] in Australia.²

The editors of the two Catholic newspapers published in Sydney during the early and middle years of the decade both saw the question of land use and ownership as the issue most central to the future development of the colony. Both men believed that it was possible to build in the colony a new kind of society, free of the evils of the old world, that the good society would be based on independent yeoman farmers, and that its chief enemies were the large squatters. The consistency with which they maintained these convictions throughout the '40s makes them unique among the colonial press.

William Augustine Duncan was founding editor of Australia's first Catholic newspaper, *The Australasian Chronicle*, which was established largely to defend Catholic interests³ but which quickly assumed the role of voice of ‘the people’ and defender of their liberty.⁴ A Scot who had read himself into Catholicism at the age of sixteen at the cost of ostracism by his family, Duncan had arrived in the colony as a teacher in 1838. Though his views were often singular, and increasingly out of sympathy

¹ James Waldersee, *Catholic Society in New South Wales, 1788–1860* (Sydney: Sydney University Press, 1974), 218–19.

² Robin Gollan, *Radical and Working Class Politics: A Study of Eastern Australia, 1850–1910* (Parkville, Vic.: Melbourne University Press, 1960), 5–6.

³ *AC*, 2 August 1839.

⁴ *AC*, 3 April 1840.

thy as the Irish clergy grew more dominant in the Church, Duncan remained for most of his life the colony's [3] leading Catholic intellectual.⁵

The other editor who will feature in this study is Michael D'Arcy, an Irishman and O'Connellite who took over the *Chronicle* a few months after Duncan's dismissal in February 1844 and at about the same time as the latter started his second journal, the *Weekly Register*. While Duncan's place in Australian Catholic history is assured, and his importance as a radical spokesman in the 1840s widely recognised, D'Arcy's significance, I suggest, has been greatly underestimated. Even T.L. Suttor, who gives D'Arcy more space than most, damns him with faint psychoanalysis: his journalism, says Suttor, merely gave vent to 'his immense irritability'.⁶ I hope it will emerge during the course of this study that D'Arcy was moved by more than irritability, that, in fact, he had a reasonably coherent view of colonial politics based on the conviction he shared with Duncan that its best hope lay in comfortable independence on the land for the small man, and that he was a significant representative and spokesman for the radicalism of the 1840s.

The paucity of private papers of Catholics of this period makes it necessary to rely more than may be usual on these two papers. However, that reliance is vindicated by the particular importance of the press during the '40s, when it was the main vehicle, apart [4] from cumbersome petitions and public meetings, for the expression of opinion and the shaping of it. The *Chronicle*, in particular, was said to be read by those who often saw no other paper,⁷ to be read by a group which assembled for the purpose,⁸ and at its peak to have had a circulation second only to the *Herald*,⁹ so we may surmise that its influence was substantial. Furthermore, these two papers were important as shapers of the public image of Catholicism in the colony.¹⁰

Much is omitted from this thesis: the controversy over education, for example, is treated only briefly, and the conflict of English Benedictine clergy and the Irish majority not at all. It concentrates instead on those issues which Duncan and D'Arcy themselves identified as central to the future of the colony: the squatting system, the availability of land for the settler of modest means, and the location of economic and political power.

⁵ On Duncan see especially Margaret Payten, "William Augustine Duncan 1811–1885: A Biography of a Colonial Reformer," MA thesis (University of New South Wales, 1965).

⁶ T.L. Suttor, *Hierarchy and Democracy in Australia: The Formation of Australian Catholicism* (Melbourne: Melbourne University Press, 1965), 160.

⁷ W.A. Duncan, *Autobiography of William Augustine Duncan, Esq.*, (MS in Mitchell Library), 41–42.

⁸ Suttor, *Hierarchy and Democracy*, 76.

⁹ AC, 30 March 1841.

¹⁰ One-third of *Chronicle* subscribers were said to be 'liberal Protestants' (AC, 27 March 1841); and Duncan claimed that the *Register* went to 'nearly all that was respectable in the colony; (*Autobiography*, 57).

Chapter I

OPPOSITION TO THE SQUATTING SYSTEM

Governor Gipps published the first part of his squatting proposals—the occupation regulations¹—in the *Gazette* of 2 April 1844.² Their publication was the trigger for a storm of denunciation. Within the week 350 squatters³ and their supporters had held a protest meeting at the Royal Hotel. There the protestors were told by Mr Wentworth—the holder of 262,400 acres for two annual licences, each of £10⁴—that the Regulations were an act of ‘arbitrary violence’ upon the squatters, who had invested the wilds with value and to whom their runs were therefore a rightful inheritance.⁵ In a skilful attempt to enlist in the struggle against the Governor the varied interests of the colony, Wentworth [5] proclaimed that the licence fee was a tax fit for serfs imposed by a grab-all government; that Crown Lands belonged to the Queen only by a legal fiction, but really to the people, and that their management by the ‘representatives of the people’ was the ‘great constitutional question’; and that if squatters were made to suffer, the whole colony would suffer with them. He called for passive resistance.

Mr Benjamin Boyd, only two years in the colony but squatting on almost a million acres,⁶ and one of those men who, to the distress of the Psalmist, dream that their houses will last forever and call their lands after their own names, declared that the £150 he paid annually made the land ‘a freehold to him’ and that the new measure was ‘a premeditated spoliation’. A Mr Kemble spoke for the commercial and trading classes to say that if the squatters were squeezed all would feel the pinch.

Only Alderman Macdermott, accustomed to being the odd man out, and despite groans from the meeting and interruptions from the chairman, supported the regulations. He called for justice for the small would-be farmer, who wanted land and could not get it, and condemned dog-in-the-manger squatters who held more land than they

¹ I am following the terminology established by Stephen H. Roberts, *The Squatting Age in Australia, 1835–1847* (Parkville, Vic: Melbourne University Press, 1964), 29–240. In brief, the regulations limited the size of a squatting run to twenty square miles or 4,000 sheep, and required the payment of a separate licence fee for each run,

² *New South Wales Government Gazette*, 2 April 1844. See also Gipps’ explanatory despatches to Lord Stanley, 3 and 16 April 1844, in *Historical Records of Australia* (hereafter *HRA*), Series I, volume xxiii, 507–518, 545–549.

³ Representing the 700 squatting licences, some of which were held multiply by single individuals, then in the colony; Roberts, *The Squatting Age*, 214.

⁴ Cf. K. Buckley, ‘Gipps and the Graziers of New South Wales 1841–1846’, Part II, *Historical Studies: Selected Articles*, Series I, 92–93.

⁵ The ‘squatter theory of value’, as Michael Roe sardonically calls it; *The Quest for Authority in Eastern Australia, 1835–1851* (Parkville, Vic: Melbourne University Press, 1965), 61.

⁶ K. Buckley, ‘Gipps and the Graziers’, 92. Later work indicates Boyd may have had 1,771,880 acres; Gollan, *Radical and Working Class Politics*, 5.

could use and yet would still have small proprietors hunted out [6] after ‘dining with the Commissioner for the purpose’. Macdermott realised that the squatters, once pioneers, were becoming land monopolists:⁷ a colonial Cassandra, he saw the future, but could find no-one to believe him—not, at least, at the Royal Hotel. The meeting concluded with the formation of a Pastoral Association;⁸ of the twenty-three members of the committee, sixteen were members of the Legislative Council.⁹

Of the colonial press, only the two Catholic papers supported the Governor and the regulations. D’Arcy’s *Chronicle* found their justice and wisdom to be self-evident, and the condemnatory resolutions passed at the Royal Hotel to be ‘but verbiage’,¹⁰ although a few days later he would suggest that the regulations were poorly timed, as many squatters were still suffering the effects of the depression.¹¹ Despite this note of sympathy for the individuals involved, however, D’Arcy consistently opposed squatting itself as a ‘faulty and vicious system’.¹² [7]

Duncan’s warning in the *Register* raised the issues that would most preoccupy him in the following months:

To confer these immense runs upon the present race of squatters would be to sell ourselves and our children, and all who may in future seek a home on these shores, as the slaves of an oligarchy, which would speedily become so powerful and irresponsible that no law or government could coexist with it, but as its tools of oppression and aggrandisement... If there be any one thing expedient to be done for the future well-being of this country, it is the gradual, but firm and determined rooting up and entire reconstruction upon systematic principles, of its depasturing system. These new regulations are a step, and as far as they go, a wise and equitable step.¹³

The position taken by the *Register* and the *Chronicle* was distinctive, all the other papers having joined in the squatters’ campaign. The *Herald* stressed repeatedly that the prosperity of the colony depended on that of the graziers, and threw in the observation that the regulations would reduce the colonists to the condition of Russian serfs.¹⁴ The *Australian* also opposed the regulations and was at pains to point out that the squatters were ‘the founders of the public wealth’, though it was prepared to admit that the squatting system was ‘an anomaly’, albeit a necessary one.¹⁵ [8]

Those reactions were to be expected. More surprising, however, were the reactions of the smaller papers of radical or democratic reputation. Their responses to the regulations showed the main lines of colonial dissatisfaction with the Government

⁷ Cf. Roberts, *The Squatting Age*, 245–47.

⁸ A lengthy report of the Royal Hotel meeting is in *MC*, 17 April 1844.

⁹ *WR*, 13 April 1844.

¹⁰ *MC*, 10 April 1844.

¹¹ *MC*, 13 April 1844. This qualification was enough, however, to lose him the favour of the Governor, who later wrote to Gladstone that Duncan had been the only journalist to support the regulations; *HRA*, I.xxv, 73–74.

¹² *MC*, 24 April 1844.

¹³ *WR*, 20 April 1844.

¹⁴ *Sydney Morning Herald*, 19 April 1844; cf. also 8 February, 21 March, 9 April. For the press in the 1840s see R.B. Walker, *The Newspaper Press in New South Wales, 1803–1920* (Sydney: Sydney University Press, 1976), ch. 4.

¹⁵ *Australian*, 2 May, 15 April 1844.

and the imperial administration.¹⁶ Lang's *Colonial Observer*, which claimed to be 'the only Liberal paper in this Colony',¹⁷ took up the constitutional issue, the manner rather than the matter of the regulations: as arbitrary taxation at the caprice of the Governor, they were a step towards despotism, and it added that New South Wales was 'essentially a pastoral country'.¹⁸ G. O'Brien's threepenny *Dispatch*, generally favourable to labour interests,¹⁹ reflected the importance the struggle over land policy had acquired as a symbol of dissatisfaction with a distant and unresponsive Colonial Office:²⁰ [9] in these 'harsh, ill-timed, oppressive and ungenerous' regulations, Gipps, 'the servile instrument of a grasping minister', had sacrificed the colony to mere increase of revenue; the humbler classes should join the squatters in resisting them.²¹ The *Star and Workingman's Guardian*, a penny paper which looked forward to the 'ultimate revolution in the whole system of political economy',²² at first denounced the regulations as untimely, given the financial vulnerability of many graziers,²³ though, as we shall see, it would later be persuaded by W.A. Duncan into a change of opinion.²⁴

Most revealing of all, however, was the case of the *Guardian*, the organ of the Mutual Protection Association. Begun only in March 1844, its first issues were devoted to a long and lucid analysis of the political situation in which its editor, James McEachern, condemned the 'spirit of domination' which had made the government of the colony 'an oligarchy of stock-holders'. In 'such a crisis as this', he wrote, the middle and working classes should unite to bring about a 'just and salutary balance of power'.²⁵ [10]

A few weeks later, however, when the regulations were proclaimed, there was a different sort of response. McEachern had been suddenly deposed and his place taken by Benjamin Sutherland. All ringing talk of crisis and equilibrium was gone. Sutherland wrote lugubriously that 'in such dismal times as these' the Governor should not impose new burdens on the squatters lest the whole community be ruined.²⁶ And though within a few months the *Guardian* would be in a state of constant agitation about the dominance of pastoral interests in the Council and their

¹⁶ On the combination of interests which opposed the squatting regulations, see Buckley, 'Gipps and the Graziers', *passim*; B. Dyster, 'Support for the Squatters, 1844', *Journal of the Royal Australian Historical Society*, 51 (1965): 41-59; Peter Burroughs, *Britain and Australia, 1831-1855: A Study in Imperial Relations and Crown Lands Administration* (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1967), 296-327; Graham J. Abbott, *The Pastoral Age. A Re-Examination* (Melbourne & Sydney: Macmillan, 1971), 164-67.

¹⁷ *Colonial Observer*, 11 January 1843.

¹⁸ *Ibid.*, 11 April, 16 May 1844. Lang himself looked forward to a society of yeoman farmers. See, e.g., Gollan, *Radical and Working Class Politics*, 10-13.

¹⁹ E.g. *Dispatch*, 20 January 1844; see also Walker, *The Newspaper Press*, 39.

²⁰ Burroughs, *Britain and Australia, 1831-1855*, 279-80.

²¹ *Dispatch*, 6 and 13 April 1844.

²² *Star*, 2 March 1844.

²³ *Ibid.*, 13 April 1844.

²⁴ See below, at note 120.

²⁵ *Guardian*, 16 March 1844.

²⁶ *Ibid.*, 11 April 1844.

‘gross subserviency to class interests’,²⁷ its mind about the regulations remained the same: they are ‘unjust and extortionate’.²⁸ The main burden of Sutherland’s argument was that the regulations would only impede a general revival of the economy, which he considered completely dependent on the wool trade.²⁹ He was aware of the colony’s extensive system of credit, and of the many outstanding debts, which made the squatters’ campaign and prosperity of immediate relevance to many town dwellers.³⁰ Thus, in supporting the squatters, [11] Sutherland was prepared to put the interests of urban employees and businessmen before those of small farmers and land-seekers, and to forsake the *Guardian*’s former conviction that an anti-squatter alliance was necessary to create an equilibrium of interests.³¹ The result of this *volte-face* was a split in the Mutual Protection Association, and by year’s end both the Association and its paper were defunct.³²

If this has been a lengthy digression it has been a necessary one in order to establish the distinctiveness of the position and strategies espoused by the *Chronicle* and the *Register*. The two Catholic papers were now left as the main centres of opposition to the squatting interest and the principal champions of a weakened land movement.

In standing against this near unanimity of press opinion, Duncan and D’Arcy were consistent with their convictions about the kind of social and economic structure [12] desirable for the colony: one based not on aristocratic landowners and large capitalists, but on a nucleus of independent farmers, each ‘the owner and lord of his own farm’, which would, in turn, form the basis for a respectable class of independent artisans, merchants and manufacturers.³³ A society based on a virtuous and prosperous yeomanry was a constant in the nineteenth-century radical ideal,³⁴ and neither editor was prepared to trim this cloth to what others saw as the economic realities of the day. Asked D’Arcy rhetorically, ‘Are we to sacrifice great principles to the mere expediency of an hour?’³⁵ It was because both saw the future of the colony as intimately

²⁷ *Ibid.*, 6, 20, 27 July 1844.

²⁸ *Ibid.*, 20 July 1844.

²⁹ Though it was, in fact, also dependent on live sheep sales and therefore on continuing pastoral expansion. See S.J. Butlin, *Foundations of the Australian Monetary System, 1788–1851* (Sydney: Sydney University Press, 1953), 315–18.

³⁰ *Guardian*, 11, 20 April 1844. On mutual indebtedness see esp. B. Dyster, ‘Support for the Squatters’, 41–59.

³¹ Cf. L.J. Hume, ‘Working Class Movements in Sydney and Melbourne before the Gold Rushes’, *Historical Studies: Selected Articles*, Series II, 42–43.

³² Hume, *ibid.*, 43. See also the letter from ‘A Working Man’ condemning the MPA in *WR*, 22 June 1844. The collapse of this early and significant ‘working-class’ organisation in part explains Duncan’s later observation that it was over the land question, in the context of the depression, that the ‘elements of democracy’ lost their opportunity to make an alliance of working and middle classes against the ‘elements of aristocracy’; ‘Notes on Ten Years’ Residence in New South Wales’, *Hogg’s Instructor*, vol. 5, 147.

³³ E.g. *MC*, 3 February 1844; *AC*, 20 June 1841.

³⁴ And one that continued to exercise its appeal, especially among some Catholics, well into the present century, e.g. in England, the Laxton distributist group of the 1930s, and in Australia, the Catholic Rural Movement. See further in ch. 4.

³⁵ *MC*, 3 February 1844.

connected with the development of small farms that the land question assumed its vital significance and the battle with the squatters its almost apocalyptic tone.

Throughout the early 1840s, the squatting interest had opposed existing land policy on the grounds that New South Wales was essentially a pastoral colony, and would only develop through large-scale land-holdings and dispersed settlement. Both Duncan and D'Arcy rejected this basic contention and the plantation social structure [13] which they were convinced it would entail.³⁶ They attempted to meet the pastoralists' economic arguments by asserting that small farming would benefit the colony by stimulating agriculture, immigration and land sales, and by bringing about a more favourable balance of trade.³⁷ Duncan argued that the economics of wool growing, deprived of slave labour since the end of assignment, had now changed, and considered that attempts to base the economy on grazing were merely attempts to cling to a dead past.³⁸

He wished that 'a large proportion of the capital and industry of the Colony could be directed into channels not less profitable and yet more compatible with the advancement of civilization among the people than the present squatting system'.³⁹ He had definite proposals for growing crops such as wine grapes and olives (on both of which he published pamphlets), and for semi-Utopian self-supporting agricultural unions.⁴⁰ D'Arcy's economic arguments against the squatting system mainly stressed that, through its failure to develop agriculture, the country was dependent on foreign wheat, which he saw as a security threat as well as an unnecessary [14] drain of capital. 'Grazing will never make a great nation', he declared.⁴¹

However, the main point to the anti-squatter argument, particularly before 1844 when political elements assumed a greater importance, was not basically economic: it was based rather on the threat that squatting posed to moral and traditional values, and to the aspirations to self-advancement and independence on the land which were central both to the radical program and the immigrant ethos.⁴²

The barbarism and lawlessness said to characterise the interior, where men lived in slab hovels and the amenities of civilisation were reduced to 'mutton and damper and something to lie on', were widely deplored.⁴³ Duncan held that squatting had

³⁶ Cf. Payten, 'William Augustine Duncan', 103-104.

³⁷ E.g. *AC*, 20 February 1841; 28 May 1842; *MC*, 10 January 1844.

³⁸ *WR*, 6 January 1844. Graziers, however, were responding to the changed labour situation by increasing flock sizes and improving methods of flock management; cf. Lynnette J. Peel, *Rural Industry in the Port Phillip Region, 1835-1880* (Carlton, Vic.: Melbourne University Press, 1974), 33-36.

³⁹ *WR*, 6 January 1844.

⁴⁰ Cf. Payten, 'William Augustine Duncan', 118-121.

⁴¹ *MC*, 10 January 1844; 4 January 1845. This unfavourable trade balance was a constant theme of D'Arcy's. Although the need for increased agricultural production was genuine, problems of soil, climate and distribution made home-grown wheat more than 50% dearer than the imported product. D'Arcy was aware of this and favoured compensatory tariffs (*MC*, 16 December 1843, 13 March 1844). Cf. Burroughs, *Britain and Australia*, 105-109.

⁴² Cf. Hume, 'Working-Class Movements', 33ff.; T.H. Irving, 'Some Aspects of the Study of Radical Politics in New South Wales before 1856', *Labour History* 5 (1963): 21; Payten, 'William Augustine Duncan', 104-105.

⁴³ Cf. Roberts, *The Squatting Age*, 283. Bishop Broughton, who would later assist Gipps in

already proved itself to [15] be a brutalising occupation and feared that if the system continued the Australian bushman would become 'as barbarous as the savage and perhaps more ferocious'.⁴⁴ He and D'Arcy shared a concern for its impact on the Aborigines, on whom it visited a 'wholesale system of murder' and brought those 'English panaceas, those civiliziers—rum and bibles, and syphilis, and preachments, and strychnine, and hymns, and fusillades and rifle practice'.⁴⁵ By dispersion of settlement, squatting put stockmen beyond the influence of law, government and religion.⁴⁶ Few squatters were found who would employ a man with a family, and thus further vices were introduced to the bush.⁴⁷ Rural workers were beyond the machinery of justice that might protect them from the notorious dishonesty of their employers.⁴⁸ In all, writes D'Arcy, the system is raising up 'a savage race of depraved, untaught, vicious, half-savage men, without wife or home or attachment, except perhaps to aboriginal women, with whose husbands and fathers they wage a murderous war'.⁴⁹ It was the very antithesis of the respectability that members of the working classes were supposed to find, through frugality and industriousness, in a new land. [16]

The squatting system, indeed, made impossible that centralisation of population and development of agriculture which were thought to be essential to the health of the colony.⁵⁰ Both editors argued that wealthy squatters and landowners had conspired to limit the availability of land so that 'a class of spade-men landowners would not come between the wind and their nobility', said Duncan, and so that immigrants might be kept poor.⁵¹ D'Arcy, no less colourfully, maintained that a clique had conspired 'by secret machinery and back-door influence' with 'that Prince of Charlatans, the Kidnapper Wakefield' to deceive the imperial government and keep the land and wealth of the colony in its own hands.⁵² D'Arcy, however, (and Duncan, though to a lesser extent) failed to distinguish the different interests of squatters, who merely occupied Crown Lands by annual licence, and landowners. The situation is confused somewhat because many landowners were also squatters, but landowners in general resented squatting tenure as too easy. However, almost the whole colony opposed the £1 minimum price as too high.⁵³ A Wakefieldian conspiracy was hardly likely.

Duncan did not share D'Arcy's antipathy to Wakefield. He had supported, with Henry Macdermott, Lord Russell's [17] basically Wakefieldian fixed price experiment in 1841, thinking—mistakenly as it turned out—that it would facilitate the settlement

framing the squatting regulations, was a trenchant critic of the barbarism and irreligion of the interior; Roe, *Quest for Authority*, 19, 15.

⁴⁴ *WR*, 16 September 1843; 20 January, 2 March 1844.

⁴⁵ *WR*, 5 November 1839; *MC*, 8 June 1844. Aboriginal welfare was a frequent theme in both journals.

⁴⁶ *MC*, 20 March 1844.

⁴⁷ *WR*, 2 March 1844; *MC*, 6 April 1844.

⁴⁸ *WR*, 12 August 1843.

⁴⁹ *MC*, 1 March 1845.

⁵⁰ E.g. *AC*, 20 January 1841.

⁵¹ *WR*, 19 August 1843; *MC*, 24 January 1844.

⁵² *MC*, 10 and 24 January 1844.

⁵³ Cf. Buckley, 'Gipps and the Graziers', especially 77-80; Burroughs, *Britain and Australia*, 204-213.

of poor immigrants on their own small holdings.⁵⁴ He would later suggest that the price per acre be fixed at ten shillings, which indicates the continued attractiveness to him of some, at least, of Wakefield's ideas: Duncan favoured the solid yeoman with some capital. General opinion among the working classes, which D'Arcy shared, favoured five shillings, if not free grants.⁵⁵

Despite this difference of opinion both agreed that it was essential to hold out to the migrant the possibility of 'comfortable independence' on the land. Alienations of land made by former governors to 'sycophants, favourites, schemers and jobbers' remained a public injury, but could not now be revoked.⁵⁶ Therefore, it was all the more necessary, in the view of things shared by D'Arcy and Duncan, to ensure that in future all land be leased or sold only to those prepared to live and work on it themselves.⁵⁷

By preventing such a form of occupation, D'Arcy held that squatters and their British financiers (his *bêtes noires*), [18] had made themselves the enemies, not only of the middling farmer, but of the colony's future. A man like Mr Stanton could not find a few acres for his cattle at Twofold Bay without the police being put on him, and his wife bullied, by the Imlays, who have three times what they need.⁵⁸ The colony must choose its future: it must choose between 'landed oligarchs' living in Sydney, with 500,000 or a million acres supervised by a few 'half-savage Gauchos' and carrying about a quarter of the stock it could feed, or a nation of married men each, like Abraham, reposing under his own vine and, with his family and servants, raising up a numerous and industrious population.⁵⁹ A recurring theme in both writers is that the squatters have no national vision and little attachment to the country: they wish only to make a fortune and go 'home' and spend it, caring nothing if the country remain a wilderness. Their imaginations, said Duncan, are 'entirely circumscribed by their pockets'.⁶⁰

Unlike Duncan, who thought that religion and public life were best kept separate,⁶¹ D'Arcy argued on religious grounds that the Government was obliged to equalise opportunities for access to the land because 'the humblest man is equal in the eyes of his Creator to him who is called the highest'.⁶² He had a developed theory of the [19] rights of all to the land which recalls the medieval Christian doctrine of ownership as subordinate to the common good, and of counterbalancing rights and obligations:

The law of nature recognises no right in one man to any part of the earth's surface more than another: the earth by that law belongs to all alike.

⁵⁴ AC, 10 December 1840, 9 February 1841. In fact it was not the intention of the Colonial Office to facilitate small holdings, but rather to encourage British investment and create a labour pool to compensate for the abolition of transportation.; cf. Burroughs, *ibid.*, 228-233.

⁵⁵ WR, 18 May 1844; MC, 6 January 1844.

⁵⁶ MC, 10 February 1844; cf. WR, 20 January 1844.

⁵⁷ WR, 18 May 1844; cf. 2 March 1844; MC, 10 February 1844.

⁵⁸ MC, 11 November 1843; 1 March 1845.

⁵⁹ MC, 22 March 1845.

⁶⁰ MC, 1 March 1845; WR, 26 August 1843.

⁶¹ WR, 1 June 1844.

⁶² MC, 10 January 1844.

The ownership of land, then, is not property in the sense in which a man's arms, or his legs, or his money are his property—his land he holds vicariously as the delegate and representative of the Sovereign, and in trust for the common good of the whole people; and if a man holds one acre of land, that land brings its duties as it brings its rights, but the duties go first...⁶³

By these principles, too, the squatters stood accused.

D'Arcy was prepared, as Duncan was not, to countenance the continuation of squatting on a small scale,⁶⁴ and would, on occasion, express some sympathy for the squatter in economic difficulties because of the depression, acknowledging that the colony was, to a large extent, economically dependent on pastoralism.⁶⁵ His sympathy, however, was reserved for small graziers, who had least [20] to lose, and indeed much to gain from the squatting regulations, and who were themselves often exploited by larger graziers, who were known to sub-let for up to £1 an acre land they did not own.⁶⁶

Toward the 'shepherd princes', however, D'Arcy had no sympathy whatever, nor towards the system which under their dominion had grown into 'a sort of unnatural, unmanageable monster... pregnant with a strange progeny of errors and evil'.⁶⁷ There was something of the punitive in this attitude to the larger squatters. D'Arcy thought that if the depression brought ruin to them, it would be for the public good to see the destruction of a rotten system, however painful the process would be for individuals. The wool trade itself, he thought, would not be harmed, but would only pass into the hands of thousands of yeomen in their neat cottages.⁶⁸

Duncan agreed. Pastoralists in economic difficulties he dismissed with the terse observation that if men with [21] thousands of acres at nominal rent cannot be rich, the system is best abandoned. He welcomed any factor that would lead to the breaking up of the large estates as a step towards a more equitable distribution of the 'national wealth'.⁶⁹ The ruin of a few rich 'lords of the soil' he appears to have viewed as a sort of national purgation.

This cavalier attitude to the large graziers distinguished the *Chronicle* and the *Register* from the rest of the colonial press, which was concerned with the effect of a continuing rural decline on the overall health of the economy. The real corollary of

⁶³ MC, 10 February 1844.

⁶⁴ MC, 2 July 1845. He would later welcome reports that eight-year leases with the right of pre-emption were to be granted as wholly in accord with the principle of Gipps' regulations; MC, 6 August 1845.

⁶⁵ E.g. MC, 24 April, 11 May, 2 October 1844.

⁶⁶ The two sets of regulations (the occupation regulations of April and purchase regulations of May) did not disadvantage squatters with less than twenty square miles. Taken together, they would have had the effect of breaking up large estates and making land from them available to smaller settlers with some security of tenure, pre-emption rights and compensation for improvements, as many of them realised in May (cf. letters of 'A Friend to Squatting' and Edmund Doyle, MC, 8, 11 May 1844). In Buckley's view, Gipps made a tactical error in not bringing the regulations down together, allowing the campaign of the large squatters to gain considerable momentum.; 'Gipps and the Graziers', 82-88.

⁶⁷ MC, 20 March 1844.

⁶⁸ MC, 28 October, 7 February 1844.

⁶⁹ WR, 19 August 1843.

the position espoused by Duncan and D'Arcy was a subsistence agriculture. This they may have been prepared to accept, but in the view of those with a wider perspective it must have appeared as wilful irresponsibility.

There was in the *Chronicle*, moreover, a note of class hostility not evident in the *Register*. D'Arcy did not hide his contempt for what he called the '*fruges consumere nati*—the classes born only to eat',⁷⁰ and when Mr Robinson suggested in the Legislative Council that ignorance was the cause of crime, the *Chronicle* exploded: [22]

Is not poverty [its cause]? Nakedness? Sharp hunger? A wretched, houseless, starving family?... Ages of misrule and oppression producing poverty, degradation, and baseness of spirit among the people—these are what cause crime and not want of maths!... Make equitable laws under which the labourers' hire is not ROBBED from him by the tax gatherer (the agent of the privileged classes)—feed him—clothe him—then man will commit few crimes.⁷¹

In all this D'Arcy perhaps was reflecting his Irish background, as he did also in his attacks on the landlordism implicit in large landholdings: in Ireland, he said, people were evicted from their farms to perish of cold, famine and despair; a system which produced such evils had no place in the new hemisphere.⁷² It was to Ireland that he referred to justify his support for squatter claims for fixity of tenure, the same claim, he pointed out, as O'Connell was making for the tenants of Ireland.⁷³ Duncan also recognised the desirability of security of tenure because of the encouragement it gave to the establishing of the amenities of civilisation. He feared, however, how great the pretensions of the squatters would become if granted it: 'If the squatters under a merely annual licence—a simple toleration to occupy public lands—already talk of their lands as their "inheritance" [23] and "freehold", what would they not do under "fixity of tenure"?'⁷⁴ For this reason, he welcomed the purchase regulations as an almost ideal resolution of the problem, as they granted fixity of tenure in a manner which made it virtually impossible for great landholders to take advantage of it.⁷⁵

In March 1844, shortly before the appearance of the occupation regulations, D'Arcy summarised his opposition to the squatting system. It was 'the very reverse of what is to be desired: *concentration, agriculture, population and marriage*'.

Every other interest is sacrificed to these flockowners... Our lands are grasped in immense runs (some of them almost provinces) held by single individuals: our country kept in a state of dispeoplement by them: our public morality all through the wide bush laughed to scorn: false principles disseminated... immigrants with capital and families *barred out*.⁷⁶

⁷⁰ MC, 7 February 1844.

⁷¹ MC, 9 October 1844.

⁷² MC, 10 February 1844.

⁷³ MC, 13 April 1844.

⁷⁴ WR, 13 April 1844.

⁷⁵ WR, 18 May 1844. These regulations restricted the size of a run and required the purchase of a homestead block on each if multiple runs were held. Buckley calculates that Benjamin Boyd, with the equivalent of 60 runs, would have had to pay £19,200 every eight years, or £2,400 annually, or more, depending on the operation of the auction system; 'Gipps and the Graziers', 92-93.

⁷⁶ MC, 20 March 1844.

‘Of what use are such men in a national sense’, he asked, ‘compared with an army of small proprietors, with their wives, children, servants, tradesmen, etc., and “all the busy hum of men”?’⁷⁷ The practicality of this ideal was [24] not considered. When ‘O.S.B.’ wrote to the *Chronicle* to report that concentration of population was not possible on the ‘dreary barren ranges’, D’Arcy called him a ‘worthy writer’, but did not falter in the fervour with which he proclaimed the excellence of the small farm ideal.⁷⁸

The proclamation of the regulations and the intensive squatter campaign against them prompted a change of emphasis in the opposition of both editors to the squatting system. Duncan had long since warned of what he considered the oligarchic ambitions of the ‘squattocracy’,⁷⁹ and the vehemence of the campaign inaugurated at the Royal Hotel confirmed him in that opinion.

What now became central to Duncan’s argument was the assertion that by challenging the power of the Governor to dispose of Crown Lands, the squatters were challenging the principle that such lands were held in trust for the good of the whole community.⁸⁰ By thus denying the rights of both Crown and people, the squatters risked destroying the balance of society. Therefore, he held, the squatting claims represented an ‘incipient revolution’.⁸¹ ‘Shall the Queen or the squatters reign?’, he asked, warning that the power and prerogative of the Crown was the main safeguard against the oppression of one part of society by another.⁸² [25]

The constitutional question—that the regulations had been promulgated without the advice of the Legislative Council—which had been sufficient to bring Dr Lang, no friend to squatters, into the opposition, he dismissed:

The pretence of our ‘patriots’ that they are fighting with the government the battle of the constitution is a false pretence to cover their design of appropriating to their own use the public lands of the colony and reducing its inhabitants to slavery. Their insisting on a high qualification for the elective franchise on the one hand, while they harrass and weaken the government on the other, ought to satisfy every enquiring mind that what they seek is unlimited power for themselves and their class.⁸³

On this basis, Duncan could take as his central position that the land struggle was one between a faction and ‘the people’, ‘a contest between the public and a few half-ruined monopolists, between justice and injustice, between morality and vice...’⁸⁴ This analysis was consistent with Duncan’s somewhat oversimplified view of colonial society and politics, in which he saw replayed the old European conflict of aristocracy and people.⁸⁵ The importance of land and the political ambitions of the large landowners and squatters made it natural to cast them as the villains of the piece and to

⁷⁷ Ibid.

⁷⁸ MC, 25 May 1844.

⁷⁹ AC, 10 September 1839.

⁸⁰ WR, 13 April 1844.

⁸¹ WR, 14 December 1844; a position he had anticipated a year earlier: WR, 21 October 1843.

⁸² WR, 14 December 1844.

⁸³ WR, 28 December 1844.

⁸⁴ WR, 13 April 1844.

⁸⁵ Cf. Payten, ‘William Augustine Duncan’, 159.

assume a natural [26] alliance between the middle and working classes against them.⁸⁶ However, the real situation was more complex, as the broad support for the squatters' protest and the split in the Mutual Protection Association had shown.

Duncan was sufficiently perspicacious to see that the squatters had enlisted in their cause a number of otherwise conflicting interests.⁸⁷ He attempted to exploit these differences, making appeals in turn to the various interest groups: he urged merchants not to sacrifice long-term interests to immediate gain;⁸⁸ he drew the distinction, as Macdermott had done at the Royal Hotel, between the interests of large and small squatters;⁸⁹ he tried to drive a wedge between landowners within the boundaries and squatters without by saying that easy leases would further depress land values.⁹⁰

D'Arcy was in basic agreement. The squatters, he wrote, were attempting to use possession of the land as a means to political power, their aim a 'degrading political thralldom'. They are a faction which wants to become 'an *Imperium in imperio* not only able to ride [27] roughshod over the people of the colony, but to defy the crown itself'. This 'mighty crisis' 'must bring about a trial of strength between the Queen and the squatters'.⁹¹

To the Governor as viceregent, he looked for the defence of the common good against the pretensions of a narrow class. 'On Sir George Gipps', he wrote, 'depends which of the two future Australias our sons and grandsons shall have'.⁹² And though he had previously criticised both the Governor—for his failure to encourage small farms⁹³—and the Colonial Office—which had 'utterly mistaken the nature of the colony'⁹⁴—he now looked to both as the chief safeguards of the true interests of the colony. He called for an enquiry by English gentlemen, 'of too high a grade to stoop to familiarity with the Australian aristocracy', as a solid basis for imperial legislation.⁹⁵ Before long he was defending himself against a charge of being a 'Government hack'.⁹⁶

D'Arcy was not entirely consistent in his approach to a political solution, unable as he was to decide between a free legislature or imperial management.⁹⁷ In [28] part, this was a recognition of the current political realities, given that the supposed representatives of the people had proved the narrowness of their class interests. However, it was also, in part, an unresolved political conservatism not uncharacteristic of con-

⁸⁶ Hume, 'Working Class Movements', 44.

⁸⁷ Cf. Buckley, 'Gipps and the Graziers', 86-88.

⁸⁸ *WR*, 13 April 1844.

⁸⁹ *Ibid.*

⁹⁰ *WR*, 26 April 1845. This crucial alliance of interests did, in fact, begin to collapse in 1846, but by then the squatters' aims were all but gained in London; Buckley, 'Gipps and the Graziers', 79, 100-102.

⁹¹ *MC*, 8 May 1844; 28 June 1845.

⁹² *MC*, 1 March 1845.

⁹³ *MC*, 10 January 1844.

⁹⁴ *MC*, 2 March 1844.

⁹⁵ *MC*, 5 July 1845.

⁹⁶ *MC*, 16 July 1845.

⁹⁷ *MC*, 30 April 1845.

temporary 'radical' politics.⁹⁸ Given his views on the franchise,⁹⁹ D'Arcy was curiously reluctant to call for popular resistance to the squatters.¹⁰⁰ While Duncan castigated an apathetic public and called for the formation of a 'loyal party' representative of the people, and the removal of the Wentworth/Windeyer clique from a position they had abused,¹⁰¹ D'Arcy wrote placidly of standing between 'oligarchical faction and democratical fury' and urged his readers to devote themselves to the pursuit of wealth, independence and virtue rather than to politics.¹⁰² It was not until October 1846, over the revival of transportation, that he would overcome his aversion to 'unnecessary political agitation' sufficiently to call for the formation of a popular anti-squatting association, an issue on which, coincidentally or not, his uncle Father McEncroe had decided views.¹⁰³ [29]

D'Arcy thought that the absence of agitation during 1845 indicated that the faction was defeated,¹⁰⁴ but Duncan recognised that the battle had only shifted to London. By now the strength of the opposition was prodigious: the local legislature, a carefully orchestrated committee of inquiry (the Committee on Crown Land Grievances), most of the local press, a new journal (Robert Lowe's *Atlas*), a parliamentary agent in London, and a lobby of English manufacturers and importers. Even the Madras *Athenaeum* had joined the fray.¹⁰⁵ Duncan warned that 'no government can for a long time withstand such an organised agitation as this, unless a counter movement be made by the people in their own defence',¹⁰⁶ but he warned in vain.

When, eventually, the Imperial Act of December 1846 and the Order-in-Council of March 1847 resolved the squatting question along lines basically favourable to the squatters,¹⁰⁷ Duncan was no longer editing the *Register*, which had folded at the end of 1845. He reflected, however, in reminiscences written in 1849, that the question was far from settled and predicted that the agitation to regain the land would be as great as that by which it was usurped.¹⁰⁸ [30]

Indeed, even men once prominent in the Pastoral Association were beginning to find that things sweet to the taste may prove in digestion sour, and were realising, as Duncan and D'Arcy had done from the beginning, that at stake was not only the well-being of the squatters and the interests of those dependent on them, but the nature of colonial society and economy, and that, in Michael Roe's words, the squatters had become 'ruthless offenders against the ideal of a cooperative community'.¹⁰⁹

⁹⁸ Cf. Hume, 'Working Class Movements', 272-273.

⁹⁹ See *infra*, chapter 3.

¹⁰⁰ The Governor also declined to do anything to gather support for his policy; Gipps to Stanley, 20 October 1843, *HRA* Lxxiii, 200.

¹⁰¹ *WR*, 14 December, 28 September 1844.

¹⁰² *MC*, 6 September 1845.

¹⁰³ *SC*, 28 October 1846. Cf. B.T. Dowd, 'Archdeacon McEncroe the Anti-Transportationist', *Journal of the Australian Catholic Historical Society* 3 (1969): 11-25.

¹⁰⁴ *MC*, 3 January 1846.

¹⁰⁵ Roberts, *The Squatting Age*, 249.

¹⁰⁶ *WR*, 9 November 1844.

¹⁰⁷ Burroughs, *Britain and Australia*, 321-327.

¹⁰⁸ Duncan, 'Notes of Ten Years' Residence', 147.

¹⁰⁹ *Quest for Authority*, 64.

Even those who recognised that its prosperity was based on sheep did not want the whole colony given over to them, or the squatting system, with all its social inadequacies, to continue unreformed.¹¹⁰ Robert Lowe, whose *Atlas* had been the chief mouthpiece of the grazing interest and the bitterest critic of the Governor, declared in the Council, with Bland and Windeyer agreeing, that they had all been in error, that the Order-in-Council was a triumph for the right of the strong to take and keep all they could grasp, and that the colony might be ‘a sheep-walk forever’.¹¹¹

D’Arcy agreed: after a fourteen-year lease no government would be able to eject a squatter, and the patrimony of all would have passed into the hands of a few. He had changed his opinion about small squatting leases and free grants, and now called for the complete [31] abolition of squatting and the sale of land at a fair price to small capitalists as the only path to prosperity.¹¹² News of famine in Ireland, where the living were too weak to bury the dead, made the ‘locking of the land’ seem all the more tragic.¹¹³ He urged action, but it was too late. It was only with the changed circumstances of society after the gold rushes that it became possible to make another attempt at establishing the small man on the land.¹¹⁴

Something must be said about the significance of the stand taken by the *Chronicle* and the *Register*. Duncan thought that his opposition to the squatters’ ‘enterprise of confiscation’ had been the ‘grand feature’ of the *Register*, whose publication had brought him honour to lighten the poverty it caused.¹¹⁵ Not a man to underestimate his own importance, Duncan claimed to be the main influence in winning support for the regulations in the weeks after their first appearance.¹¹⁶ His claim to have been the only voice raised against the squatters brought a mocking rejoinder from D’Arcy, who compared him to ‘the three tailors of Tooley-street, who began their address with “We, the people of England”’.¹¹⁷ [32] Indeed, Duncan seems to have been inclining his ear to no tongue but his own, for he overlooked not only the policy of the *Chronicle*, but the speech of his friend Macdermott at the Royal Hotel.

Nevertheless, the *Register* had its influence. Some thought it sufficiently important to attempt to change its course by bribery.¹¹⁸ Gipps ensured that copies went to Lord Stanley, which Duncan considered a great honour.¹¹⁹ Edmund Mason, editor of the radical *Star and Workingman’s Guardian*, found Duncan’s refutation of the squatters’ case ‘masterly’, and changed his own opinion and his paper’s policy accordingly.¹²⁰ The *Chronicle*, too, found supporters, as seen in its letters column.¹²¹ How-

¹¹⁰ Burroughs, *Britain and Australia*, 327–328.

¹¹¹ SC, 29 May 1846.

¹¹² SC, 28 July 1847.

¹¹³ SC, 28 July, 7 August 1847.

¹¹⁴ D.W.A. Baker, ‘The Origins of Robertson’s Land Acts’, *Historical Studies: Selected Articles*, Series I, 103–126.

¹¹⁵ Duncan, *Autobiography*, 58, 56.

¹¹⁶ WR, 20 April 1844.

¹¹⁷ MC, 24 April 1844.

¹¹⁸ Duncan, *Autobiography*, 58.

¹¹⁹ Gipps to Stanley, 17 April 1844; HRA I.xxiii, 549; WR, 6 April 1844.

¹²⁰ *Star*, 26 and 27 April 1844; he quotes a series of six questions from WR, 6 April 1844.

¹²¹ E.g., letters of ‘Verax’, 1 May 1844; ‘A Friend to Squatting’, 8 May; Edmund Doyle, 11 May.

ever, Duncan had to admit that he lost subscriptions over the squatting issue, not surprising in view of the 'respectable' character of its subscribers.¹²²

The extent to which the position of the two papers reflected the views of the majority of Catholics, rather than those of two individuals, is problematic. It is [33] unlikely that Duncan and D'Arcy were in consultation with each other: apart from the natural rivalry of competitors there was little love lost between them. Duncan still resented the circumstances in which he lost the editorship of the *Australasian Chronicle* to D'Arcy, who had changed its name 'with a view', said Duncan, 'as he was not ashamed to confess in a public court, of defrauding me of my title of joint proprietor'.¹²³

The *Chronicle* was the semi-official organ of the Church, but there is no evidence of an official attitude corresponding to its policy on this question. In contrast to the education controversy, which absorbed so much Catholic attention during the second half of 1844, there were no public meetings called, no official statement from the Archbishop. Possibly the clergy's lack of interest in the land question is an explanation, for the education campaign was largely a clergy-led affair.¹²⁴ Even the redoubtable Father McEncroe, who edited the *Chronicle* from February to October 1843, had no comments on the land question, nor are there any in his surviving papers;¹²⁵ indeed, he welcomed the election of Wentworth and Bland, Duncan's chief squattocrat bogies, to the Legislative Council.¹²⁶ [43]

Prominent Catholics were to be found of both opinions: Caroline Chisolm was an advocate of small farms and an enemy to squatting.¹²⁷ Roger Therry supported Gipps, with some reservations;¹²⁸ but Henry O'Brien, a prominent layman, was a member of the Pastoral Association.¹²⁹ Ordinary Catholics probably suffered from the apathy of which Duncan constantly complained in the general population, or else looked to their own interests: Michael Ryan, for example, who arrived penniless from Tipperary in 1821, supported squatting because it had enabled him to acquire 2,500 acres, 1,200 cattle and 4,000 sheep; but Denis Hickey, who came from Limerick in 1839, found that 'It's the sheep masters that has the lands entirely... the poor man can't get it, [not even] the few acres a poor man wants to keep his children, God bless them'.¹³⁰

The land policy espoused by Duncan and D'Arcy and the opposition to pastoralism it entailed contained a number of contradictions, not the least of which was that in the name of radicalism and a new society it clung to a backward-looking ideal unrespon-

¹²² Duncan, *Autobiography*, 150. I can find no evidence relating to the effect on *Chronicle* subscriptions.

¹²³ Duncan, *Autobiography*, 54–55.

¹²⁴ Cf. J.M. O'Brien, 'Catholics and Politics in New South Wales 1835–1870', (MA thesis, University of Newcastle, 1965).

¹²⁵ McEncroe Papers. Saint Mary's Cathedral Archives, Sydney.

¹²⁶ AC, 17 June 1843,

¹²⁷ Roe, *Quest for Authority*, 73.

¹²⁸ Therry, *Reminiscences*, 243–253.

¹²⁹ O'Brien, 'Catholics and Politics', 197.

¹³⁰ Patrick O'Farrell, 'Some Caroline Chisolm Correspondence 1845–1849', *Australasian Catholic Record* 54 (1977): 323.

sive to the real situation of the colony. Nevertheless, in arguing that a pastoral society was the antithesis of the hopes of the small man and calling for a program aimed at creating a new society [35] organised for the benefit of all classes, they made a significant contribution to the political culture of the colony. As the decade progressed and the nature of pastoralist ambitions became more evident, the radical ideal gained support among the growing middle class. Thus the movement of which Duncan and D'Arcy had been the most consistent spokesmen provided a link between the radicalism of the '40s and the liberal movement of the following decades.¹³¹

¹³¹ Cf. Irving, 'Radical Politics', 21.

Chapter II

LABOUR AND THE DEPRESSION

Opposition to the squatting interest, and to the kind of society its victory was thought to entail, had a positive counterpart in the two editors' support for labour interests and those of the poorer settlers. Both journals attracted letters from readers which indicate that they were popularly regarded as spokesmen for the working classes.¹

In the first issue of the *Register* Duncan was explicit about his intention to be a champion of labour interests. The 'moderate conservatism' of other journals he eschewed as merely 'as much oppression of the many by the few as the spirit of the age will bear'. His own program he professed to draw, as he did the title of the *Register*, from the English radical William Cobbett: 'There are always men enough to plead the cause of the rich, enough and enough to echo the woes of the rich; but be it your part to show compassion for those who labour, and to maintain their rights.'² [37]

Duncan's position as a spokesman for labour was qualified by the element of condescension often evident in his attitudes, by his horror of class legislation,³ and by his growing conservatism, born of disappointment. He was dismayed at the apathy of the people, particularly in their failure to form an anti-squatting alliance in 1844, for he was a man inclined to ascribe views not in agreement with his own to lack of political acumen.⁴ Nevertheless, his credentials as a spokesman for the working classes were well-established at the time he began the *Register*, as is evident in the trade society support with which the journal was established.⁵

His political reputation went back to the early days of the *Australasian Chronicle*. In 1840 he had 'launched the thunders of the press' in the emancipist cause during the 'pure Merino' campaign against them. He opposed Gipps' Corporation Bill, which excluded emancipists from public office and restricted their franchise, and James Macarthur's 'inquisitorial' Census, measures which obviously had serious political

¹ E.g., *AC*, 29 June 1841: 'the only journal which vindicates the cause of the working man; 7 January 1843; *MC*, 1 May, 20 November 1844. The term 'working classes' I have used throughout to apply to wage-earners and independent manual workers, the contemporary usage in the 1840s; Hume, 'Working Class Movements'. But cf. the warning remarks in R.W. Connell and T.H. Irving, *Class Structure in Australian History: Documents, Narrative and Argument* (Melbourne: Longman Cheshire, 1980), 75.

² *WR*, 29 July 1843. On Cobbett, see John Clarke, *The Price of Progress: Cobbett's England, 1780-1835* (London: Hart-Davis MacGibbon, 1977).

³ 'In all ages one of the greatest evils that has afflicted society'; *WR*, 29 July 1843.

⁴ *WR*, 7 December 1844; and see further *infra*, chapter 3.

⁵ *Guardian*, 13 July 1844. The shoemakers gave £10/2/6, the united printers £5, and the associated stonemasons decided against £20 by only one vote. Cf. Leila Thomas, 'The Development of the Labour Movement in the Sydney District of New South Wales', (MA Thesis, University of Sydney, 1919), 8.

consequences for Catholics.⁶ Duncan boasted that his [38] opposition to these measures, along with that of Henry Macdermott, had been decisive in defeating the exclusive campaign.⁷ It is worth noting in passing, however, that Duncan, unlike many Catholics, had no natural attachment to the emancipist cause. As a Scot and a convert he did not identify with Irish clannishness; in fact, like Polding, deplored it.⁸ He despised the emancipist proprietors of the *Chronicle* as 'illiterate and to the last degree unprincipled' and, with a self-righteousness that was characteristic, refused to mix socially with them.⁹

Duncan himself acknowledged that he had been able to bring effective pressure to bear on behalf of the emancipists because of his influence with a now considerable body of opinion, that of the free immigrant workers.¹⁰ He had, indeed, attained a position of prominence, if not temporary leadership,¹¹ in the working men's movement by [39] his part in the campaign in the last months of 1840 against the proposed Masters and Servants legislation. Thus he played an important part in the first effective appearance of organised labour in Australia.¹² A series of articles in the *Chronicle* condemning the Bill as a piece of 'Gothic tyranny' and the 'most monstrous enactment we have ever heard' raised the alarm.¹³ A protest meeting, which included a vote of thanks to Duncan for bringing the matter to public attention, and a petition of 3,000 signatures was organised, and the Bill was amended to the satisfaction of the operative group.¹⁴ Duncan found himself a labour hero, and was presented with a testimonial dinner and a gold medal of four ounces worth £30, inscribed with the names of ten associated trades.¹⁵

Duncan was elated with the success of the protest:

Henceforth may be dated the time when public opinion was first unequivocally expressed in this country—the time when a PEOPLE first manifested their existence among us—the time when the real colonists, the real producers of wealth, first informed the drones of the hive... that the latter were but drones, and that they were the men by whose labour and industry alone the colony could prosper, through whom alone it could be ruled in peace.¹⁶ [40]

⁶ AC, 5 December 1840.

⁷ Duncan, *Autobiography*, 36–37.

⁸ Suttor, *Hierarchy and Democracy*, 57.

⁹ His contempt was made more complete by the attempts of some proprietors to involve the *Chronicle* in false advertising. One even asked Duncan to write a geological article hinting that there was coal in land the proprietor was about to sell! *Autobiography*, 29, 41–42.

¹⁰ *Autobiography*, 38: 'It was by supporting the latter when aggrieved that I was to bring so much pressure to bear upon the case of the emancipists.'

¹¹ Acknowledged by Ian Turner, *In Union is Strength: A History of Trade Unions in Australia, 1788–1978*, 2nd ed. (Melbourne: Nelson, 1978), 16–17.

¹² Brian Fitzpatrick, *A Short History of the Australian Labour Movement* (Melbourne: Rawson's Bookshop, 1944), 74.

¹³ AC, 24 and 29 September 1840. The Bill proposed three months' jail for crimes such as rudeness, slackness or imperfect work, on complaint from a master.

¹⁴ AC, 29 September, 20 October 1840.

¹⁵ Payten, 'William Augustine Duncan', 82–83.

¹⁶ AC, 1 October 1840.

However, it is important to note, as Margaret Payten points out, that like other middle-class radicals of the time, Duncan could support the operative campaigns without subscribing to any particular labour ethos.¹⁷ For him the victory in the Masters and Servants case was not a labour victory, but one of liberal principle over the convict ethos. Assuming the identity of middle- and working-class interests, he pursued his own concerns: one was a conviction about social justice, somewhat abstractly conceived, which called him to 'guard one part of society against the oppression of the other part';¹⁸ another was establishing in the colony 'the liberties of British subjects';¹⁹ another the conviction that the survival of a slave mentality from convict days, brutalising both master and servant alike, was a major obstacle to the development of the new society in New South Wales.²⁰

Duncan had typical *laissez-faire* views about wages and was not entirely easy about working-class combination. Special laws in favour of the working classes, he wrote in 1843, at the height of the depression, would have to be condemned, as any class legislation would have to be condemned. 'Wages, like everything else, ought, in a sound state of things, to be regulated by the supply and [41] the demand'.²¹ He was prepared to concede, however, that because of the depression the colony was not enjoying a sound state of things, and so he would countenance such regulatory measures as unemployment relief through a program of public works.²²

Duncan spelled out his views on combination at length in an article of 26 August 1843:

In all communities where the bulk of the population are divided into the classes of employers and workmen... the interests of the parties are in one respect essentially opposed to each other. The latter class naturally desire to get as much as they can for their labour, the former to give as little as possible; and each, respectively, is disposed, on particular occasions, to combine to raise or reduce the rate of wages. So long as each combination seeks to effect its object by the means strictly and justly at its own disposal the other has no reason to complain.²³

Workers, he held, could strike, and employers replace workers with machinery, but workers cannot enforce a strike on others, nor employers use public money to further their own interests.²⁴ For this reason Duncan opposed vehemently the attempts of wealthy interests in the Legislative Council to introduce a flood of migrants, which he considered a deliberate manoeuvre to create a labour surplus and permanently depress wages, a scheme [42] 'mean, sordid and selfish' and 'contrary to Justice and the rights of society'.²⁵

¹⁷ 'William Augustine Duncan', 85–88.

¹⁸ Part of a motto from Alexander Hamilton which preceded the leading article in every issue of the *Register*.

¹⁹ AC, 29 September 1840.

²⁰ AC, 24 September 1840.

²¹ WR, 12 August 1843.

²² WR, 28 September 1843.

²³ WR, 26 August 1843.

²⁴ Ibid.

²⁵ Ibid.

Duncan had aligned himself since 1841 with the operatives' continuing campaign to protect the value of their labour from the various threats posed to it. By now the political situation of 1840 was radically changed: the hostility between exclusives and emancipists had given way to a new alliance of wealthy interests made possible, to Duncan's great disgust, by the 'blackest ingratitude' on the part of wealthy emancipists, who forsook the immigrants who had supported them in 1840 to join with conservatives in opposing a low franchise.²⁶ Thus to the unemployment created by the depression was added the threat to labour in the new Legislative Council, and in schemes to introduce coolies, to revive transportation and assignment and to expand immigration. There was considerable employer agitation, because the end of assignment and the reluctance of immigrants—often skilled workers—to take pastoral jobs in the country (where stories told of extortionate masters adding 500-800% to the price of clothing and rations, and paying stockmen with worthless orders) had created a labour shortage in the interior at the same time there was unemployment in the city. [43]

Duncan opposed the employer remedies: coolies,²⁷ renewed transportation²⁸ and expanded immigration.²⁹ His prominence in this continuing struggle is seen in his being placed in the chair at a meeting of 5,000 operatives over the coolie question in 1843.³⁰

Duncan's and D'Arcy's economic views are revealed chiefly in their analyses of the economic crisis of the early '40s. By 1841 the effects of the depression were being felt everywhere in the colony. Wool prices had been falling since 1837, but of more significance was the slowing of pastoral expansion and therefore of the market for live sheep. The situation was worsened by the labour shortage and the anxiety caused to employers by the cessation of transportation. Sales of Crown Land fell from £324,072 in 1840 to £18,312 in 1842 and £9,174 in 1844, and with this decline funds for assisted immigration were dried up. What Butlin calls the colony's 'extremity of optimism' had led to rapid inflation of stock and property values and heavy speculative investment, which had tied up the colony's capital without stimulating much real production. As prices started to fall and British investors looked for their returns, pressure on borrowers for repayment snowballed and the situation rapidly turned [44] to disaster: in 1842 there were 600 insolvencies and in early 1843 the banks began to fail.³¹

Colonial opinion was almost unanimous in blaming the depression on government policy: on the maintenance of a high minimum land price and the restriction of the availability of land, which was said to have stimulated speculation; on large Government deposits in local banks, said to have encouraged too liberal credit; on the sudden withdrawal of deposits in 1841-42; and on the excessive export of capital to finance immigration.³² There were some, however, who also blamed the spirit of wild

²⁶ *Autobiography*, 42-43.

²⁷ AC, 1 July 1841.

²⁸ WR, 12 August 1843.

²⁹ AC, 16 December 1841.

³⁰ AC, 17 January 1843.

³¹ Cf. Butlin, *Foundations of the Australian Monetary System, 1788-1851*, 315-27; Peel, *Rural Industry*, 31 ff.

³² Burroughs, *Britain and Australia, 1831-1855*, 252-64.

speculation and extravagance which had made 'champagne the common beverage of bullock drivers' and pushed the price of a sheep to £3 and a horse to a hundred guineas, prices only sustained by the superabundance of English capital. The same people were inclined to excuse the Governor on the grounds that his policies had usually been recommended by the people who now blamed him for them.³³

Governor Gipps himself blamed not the outflow of capital from the colony, but the inflow of surplus capital and the speculation it encouraged.³⁴ The *Register* agreed. Thereby it differed from most of the colonial press in [45] not blaming Government policy for the depression. Duncan, who claimed to have read 'nearly everything that has been written on political economy',³⁵ was confident that the cause would be found in overcapitalisation, and that the real responsibility lay with those whose greed had led them into wild speculations, borrowing and insolvency.³⁶ What community of 150,000, he asked, needed a capital of £3 million, seven banks and two English trust Companies, a view which coincided with the Governor's.³⁷

It was basically a moral rather than an economic argument Duncan's convictions about the virtue of a small-farming society led him naturally to an anti-capitalist stance, which seems to have been hardened by an innate hostility to wealth and conspicuous spending, whose companions he declared, were selfishness, tyranny and prejudice.³⁸ If the most virtuous members of society to Duncan were working farmers, the most contemptible were 'speculators in large tracts' and 'ten per cent usurers'.³⁹ If government policies were at fault, it was only because of the agitation of those 'reckless and unprincipled scramblers after wealth' who had engineered a high minimum land price, and arranged cheap labour for themselves by using public money for immigration, measures of which they now complained.⁴⁰ [46]

Duncan opposed during 1843 most of the measures, such as the Insolvency Act ('Burton's Purge') and the Usury Bill, designed to give financial relief to pastoral and mercantile interests. The former, for example, which allowed debtors in certain circumstances to delay creditors until their position had improved, he condemned as a piece of class legislation designed only to protect wealthy speculators from the consequences of their own folly at the expense of smaller men. He thought that the burden would only be shifted to small tradesmen who would be unable to collect their debts, and that it would prolong the existence of unsound investments.⁴¹ He approved the Liens on Wool Act, however, which by changing the borrowing power of squatters, proved to be the most important measure taken to ease their financial difficulties.⁴²

Duncan's insensitivity to the economic misfortunes of the wealthy was determined in part by the hope that their distress would provide a lesson that only patient,

³³ R. Therry, *Reminiscences of Thirty Years' Residence in New South Wales*, Australian Historical Reprints (Sydney: Sydney University Press, 1974 [orig. 1863]), 226–30.

³⁴ Cf. Burroughs, *Britain and Australia*, 264.

³⁵ Letter to S.A. Donaldson, quoted in Payten, 'William Augustine Duncan', 281.

³⁶ *WR*, 7 December 1844.

³⁷ *WR*, 2 September 1843; Roberts, *The Squatting Age*, 195.

³⁸ *AC*, 20 September 1840.

³⁹ *WR*, 20 January 1844.

⁴⁰ *WR*, 19 August 1843.

⁴¹ E.g. *WR*, 12 August 1843; cf. Payten, 'William Augustine Duncan', 115.

⁴² *WR*, 12 August 1843. Cf. Butlin, *Monetary System*, 340–344

honest industry, not loans or high finance, would bring prosperity to the colony.⁴³ He welcomed the depression, as he would welcome the squatting regulations, and for a similar reason: he thought that its effect would be to break up the structures by which an elite dominated the colony and so allow a redistribution of wealth and power, [47] to the great benefit of the community at large. To this effect he quoted Dr Whatley's Lectures on Political Economy:

If a large proportion of the wealth of the community consists in the overgrown fortunes of a few, that community by no means has such promising prospects in respect of the moral and intellectual advancement of the rest of the people, or even of the possessors of these fortunes, with one that enjoys a greater diffusion of wealth.⁴⁴

It is clear that Duncan allowed his view of the desirable society to be the final determinant of his opinions, even when this allowed the opponents of the radical ideal to picture it as incompatible with the return of prosperity to the colony.⁴⁵

D'Arcy, too, saw the wealthy as basically dispensable. He attempted to argue, for example, that as the squatters were 'mere exporters', their economic significance was much over-rated.⁴⁶ In fact, he maintained, by inhibiting the development of manufacturing and agriculture, squatting promoted a drain of capital from the colony, particularly to buy grain,⁴⁷ but also for such luxuries as Swedish and American furniture ('in a land which is a forest!') and reindeer and ox tongues ('in a colony that does not know what to do with its beef or mutton!').⁴⁸ [48]

Duncan even welcomed the bank failures of 1843, for familiar reasons:

The remedy for this state of things is in the decay, and breaking up, of the institutions themselves; a result distressing no doubt, to the actual sufferers, but which afford a valuable lesson to the public... The respectable and industrious portion of society may derive advantage from the change caused by the ruin of the monopolists, gamblers and smugglers aforesaid.⁴⁹

That Duncan can have been so nonchalant about the bank failures is extraordinary, for he must have been aware, as the Governor was, that only government intervention had prevented the collapse of the Savings Banks, at a time when many of the unemployed were living entirely off their savings.⁵⁰

Duncan's views on banking and capital investment were mild, however, compared to D'Arcy's. He conducted a vigorous campaign of rhetoric against industrial capitalism which is perhaps best characterised, to use a phrase Hovell applies to Chartism, as a 'passionate negation'.⁵¹ Although there was little or no organised Chartism in Australia because there was little industrialisation, the rhetoric of English

⁴³ *WR*, 17 August 1844.

⁴⁴ *WR*, 20 January 1844.

⁴⁵ Cf. Irving, 'Radical Politics', 21.

⁴⁶ *MC*, 2 October 1844.

⁴⁷ *MC*, 28 February 1844.

⁴⁸ *MC*, 13 March 1844.

⁴⁹ *WR*, 12 September 1843.

⁵⁰ Cf. Roberts, *The Squatting Age*, 193-194.

⁵¹ Quoted in Gollan, *Radical and Working Class Politics*, 15.

radicalism was still employed by those who felt that it was possible to avoid the evils of the old world in the new. D'Arcy was one of those who believed that men are not drudges born to 'work—work—work, like four-legged animals, to the end [49] of the chapter, till death kindly removes them from a world not made for them'.⁵² In no old country had the working man ever had fair play, but here he should get it.⁵³ The first step, in D'Arcy's view, was to reject the economics of Ricardo, Lay and Adam Smith, who 'consider wealth in the hands of bankers, merchants and mill-owners to be national riches, though the millions pine in poverty and hopeless abjection'.⁵⁴ In his attacks upon capitalism D'Arcy's writing, always vigorous, approaches the lurid:

Money itself—*capital* is an engine of prodigious power... It is a monster which, in England, by *centralisation*, has swallowed almost all things into its ravenous maw—it has armed itself with the people's strength—it has clothed itself by their nakedness—and fares sumptuously every day by their famine... The modern system of centralisation, which makes machines of men, and breaks down their spirits, and energies, and hopes, and aspirations, in order that the taxes may be paid, and funds kept at a *high* figure and wages be kept low, to secure a market for manufactures, is unsound and unchristian... Did that benign and merciful Being intend that... millions of his favourite and beloved creatures should, by a faulty, vicious and corrupt system, thus be sacrificed to the moloch of wealth?⁵⁵

Such a rejection of capitalism reflects a view which, in England, was embraced as easily by the reactionary Young Englanders as by the radical Cobbett and the revolutionary Owen: a combination of the independent ideal and opposition to industrialism and its cities.⁵⁶

While Duncan thought he had identified the cause of the depression in speculation within the colony, D'Arcy saw it in an imperial context: his chief villains were the Colonial Office and English banks. He blamed the depression on the measures of the Home government: English capital, sent without its owners, to set up banks and sweep 10% home; the sudden cessation of assignment; the maintenance, 'in defiance of common sense', of the £1 minimum price; the prohibition of tariffs, which would protect and foster local agriculture and manufacturing.⁵⁷

Like Duncan, he called for reform of the colony's financial institutions, but was more specific, and, one might say, more responsible. His suggestion was an independent colonial People's Bank, offering low interest, which would be an alternative to both the 'sordid and exclusive' Bank of Australia⁵⁸ and the 'fangs of English

⁵² MC, 28 February 1844.

⁵³ MC, 7 February 1844.

⁵⁴ MC, 9 November 1844.

⁵⁵ MC, 28 February 1844.

⁵⁶ Cf. Humphrey McQueen, *A New Britannia: An Argument Concerning the Social Origins of Australian Radicalism and Nationalism*, Pelican Books (Ringwood, Vic.: Penguin Books, 1970), 120.

⁵⁷ MC, 6 January 1844.

⁵⁸ Derided for its attempt to undermine the popular Bank of NSW; MC, 19 October 1844.

mammonarchs'. 'Let our banks, our money and ourselves be Australian and then we may say all's well!'⁵⁹ [51]

As well as these banking proposals, D'Arcy's proposals for salvaging the economy involved a reduction in the land price; the consolidation of the colonial revenue (i.e., the abolition of the Wakefieldian land fund); a duty on foreign grain to encourage self-sufficiency in agriculture, and on selected imports to create employment in manufacturing; the equalisation of the price of squatting licences proportionate to size; a scheme for the settlement of families on small-holdings; and the control of immigration according to the needs of the colony.⁶⁰ It was, as is evident, a proposal based on the yeoman ideal, to which we will return in the final chapter.

At the time that D'Arcy took over the editorship of the *Chronicle* in October 1843 the effects of the depression were at their most severe, and his concern was not only with theoretical criticism of the economy, but with the plight of the unemployed. A petition of mechanics and labourers in July of that year complained that 600-700 were out of work in Sydney alone, and appealed to the Governor for relief.⁶¹ During September and October over 200 settlers left for greener pastures in Valparaiso, while a scheme to register the unemployed registered 700 in ten days, of whom 330 were given government employment on low wages of three shillings a day.⁶² [52]

Georgiana Lowe thought three shillings quite exorbitant: 'they think themselves starving on 3/- a day...', she wrote, 'but drink dreadfully and have the most improvident habits',⁶³ and the *Australian* could not believe that reports of distress were not much exaggerated; but in November a Select Committee reported 1,200 unemployed, with 2,500 dependents, almost 10% of the population.⁶⁴ The Legislative Council, meanwhile, was debating the relief, not of the unemployed, but of the pastoralists, and calling for the revival of immigration to ensure a supply of shepherds and agricultural labourers.⁶⁵

Mr Hamilton said in the Council that the operatives could not be too distressed if they could afford passages to Valparaiso and that they should be driven out of town to find employment in the interior. Mr Murray thought they were witnessing merely a 'mania for emigration' and wanted to know why, if there was unemployment, he could get no labourers on his properties.⁶⁶ Father McEncroe, presently editing the *Chronicle*, retorted: 'Let Mr Hamilton know that the meanest mechanic that handles a tool has quite as good a right as he has to remain in Sydney or go elsewhere at his own pleasure!', and added that no-one should complain of a labour shortage in the bush while workers were still regularly [53] defrauded there.⁶⁷ Doctor Lang, who, with Plunkett, was one of the few MLCs sympathetic to labour interests, remarked a

⁵⁹ MC, 10 January 1844; cf. 13 December 1843; 20 November 1844.

⁶⁰ MC, 6 January 1844.

⁶¹ AC, 18 July 1843. Many of the unemployed were skilled tradesmen, carpenters, masons, smiths, etc. G.J. Abbott, 'The Emigration to Valparaiso in 1843', *Labour History*, 9 (1970): 7.

⁶² Abbott, *ibid.*, 8-9.

⁶³ Ruth Knight, *Illiberal Liberal: Robert Lowe in New South Wales, 1842-1850* (Melbourne: Melbourne University Press, 1966), 64.

⁶⁴ Abbott, 'Valparaiso', 11.

⁶⁵ *Ibid.*, 67.

⁶⁶ AC, 9 and 27 September 1843.

⁶⁷ AC, 13 September 1843.

‘widely spreading feeling of alienation and positive hostility towards the Government and the higher classes’ among the working class.⁶⁸ Lists of new insolvents were a regular feature of the press, and bore witness to how wide a swathe had been cut through colonial prosperity.⁶⁹

The papers were remarking on an increase in suicides, like that of George Hirst, who found his affairs in an embarrassed state and shot himself through the head at his sister’s house in Glebe; and John Mahoney, an unemployed tailor, who, feeling himself a burthen on society and not wanting to live, drank poison at the Brougham Tavern, only to be saved at the hospital by tartar emetic, train oil and raw eggs.⁷⁰ The *Sydney Record* could only urge restrictions on the sale of poisons.⁷¹

The operatives of the colony petitioned in January, July, and again in October 1843 that convict labourers [54] should be removed from Sydney and their places taken by free men.⁷² Duncan agreed,⁷³ but D’Arcy, whose sympathy extended to the most unfortunate of men, did not: justice should be done to convicts, too, he said, and the free should not trample the bond.⁷⁴

D’Arcy showed more natural sympathy for the unemployed than is evident in Duncan’s writing, which, while supportive of labour interests, tended to remain on the level of high principle. In marked contrast to the cautious tone and *laissez-faire* doctrine of the *Register*, D’Arcy’s paper was full of talk of the rights of labour, which included a fair wage while working and government relief if unemployed. While Duncan tended to see justice as an abstract ideal and aim, D’Arcy demanded to see it practically expressed. Duncan had Adam Smith for his mentor and had an almost religious veneration for free trade doctrines,⁷⁵ but D’Arcy thought free trade a ‘fantastical doctrine’ which gave all the advantages to a few moneyed speculators at the expense of the working man; he took his motto from Jeremy Bentham, ‘the greatest good for the greatest number’.⁷⁶ [55]

D’Arcy wrote of the plight of the unemployed, the reasons for their distress and the remedies that should be applied with considerable poignancy and passion. Central to his argument was the conviction that, as the producers of the community’s wealth, workers have a right in justice to a fair wage:

⁶⁸ Quoted in Abbott, ‘Valparaiso’, 15-16. On Plunkett, see *MC*, 9 and 27 September 1843. Lang and Plunkett chaired the Select Committee on Distressed Mechanics and Labourers.

⁶⁹ E.g. *WR*, 29 July 1843, where the list ranged from a chemist with debts of £4,128/3/1 through graziers, farmers, merchants, and one gentleman, to a dressmaker with debts of £15/9/-.

⁷⁰ *WR*, 9 November 1844; *Star*, 20 April, 9 November 1844.

⁷¹ *Sydney Record*, 27 January 1844.

⁷² Abbott, ‘Valparaiso’, 3, 5, 10.

⁷³ *WR*, 12 August 1843.

⁷⁴ *MC*, 4 November 1843. He defended bushrangers, too, as men driven to crime by tyranny; *MC*, 1 May 1844.

⁷⁵ He considered Smith ‘the greatest writer upon political economy that ever lived’ and thought that ‘no principle in political economy is more completely established’ than free trade; *WR*, 26 August 1843, 30 March 1844.

⁷⁶ *WR*, 12 August 1843.

In a well-ordered community the rate of wages should be such that the operative may, by common exertion and moderate labour, be able to earn such wages as will enable him and his family enough of the necessaries of life to sustain them in comfort—afford the means of education to his children—and a provision for contingencies such as ill health and old age. He should also have the means from his wages of rational enjoyment, because he is the creator, if we may so speak, of everything... That the men who do all this should, after all, pine in want, or solicit the rich for food or raiment, is repugnant with reason, humanity and justice... The operative is the most valuable character in the community, and the labour of his hands should, in a sound and well-governed land, command the necessary means of support.⁷⁷

D'Arcy goes beyond Bentham in his proposals for a welfare policy, which he builds partly on the religious argument that governments, which draw their authority from God, are bound to reflect the divine care for the weak; relief for the poor is therefore a 'sacred obligation'.⁷⁸ He called on the Governor to institute 'a rational system of paternal care... a system which seeks the greatest good of the greatest number.'⁷⁹ [56]

Although D'Arcy supported the provision of £1,000 for the poor (which, he calculated, amounted to only 5/4 each) he demanded the creation of employment through public works as a preferable measure, to be financed by the £30-40,000 said to be in the Treasury or by Government debentures.⁸⁰ He had definite proposals: the sewerage of Sydney, a new Customs House, a bridge over Wallis' Creek near Maitland, a new jail at East Maitland.⁸¹ Gipps, however, with a debt of almost a million pounds in outstanding bounty orders, and haunted by the thought that he would be recalled for overspending, had no intention of authorising such large public expenditure.⁸²

Like Duncan, however, D'Arcy was convinced that the only long-term solution to the unemployment problem was the encouragement of a yeomanry on small farms. He criticised the Governor for his indifference to small farms,⁸³ although he was aware that land policy was an imperial matter. Nevertheless, he urged repeatedly that the Governor do what he could not: either to give free grants to deserving settlers or to find some way to sell small farms (of 20 to 100 acres) below the minimum upset price.⁸⁴ To D'Arcy the problem was simple: only a parchment law stood between millions of acres crying out for [57] the plough and men eager to till it.⁸⁵ Whether the

⁷⁷ MC, 25 February 1844.

⁷⁸ MC, 10 January 1844; 2 December 1843.

⁷⁹ MC, 10 January 1844. D'Arcy is not entirely consistent, making claims for natural justice on some occasions, and appealing for the observance of upper class obligations on others. Cf. Hume, 'Working Class Movements', 44-45.

⁸⁰ MC, 2 and 6 December 1843.

⁸¹ MC, 6 December 1843.

⁸² Cf. K. Grose, 'Sir George Gipps: Prince of all Skinflints?' *Journal of the Royal Australian Historical Society*, 50 (1964): 453-465; S.C. McCulloch, 'Unguarded Comments on the Administration of NSW, 1839-1846: The Gipps-Latrobe Correspondence', *Historical Studies* 9 (1959): 30-45.

⁸³ MC, 10 January 1844.

⁸⁴ MC, 18 November, 16 December 1843; 10 January 1844.

⁸⁵ MC, 21 August 1844.

unemployed carpenters and masons really wanted to cut out farms from the bush he did not stop to ask.

Not surprisingly, D'Arcy supported Wentworth's small farm scheme, which called for free grants and establishment loans as the best solution to the unemployment problem.⁸⁶ Duncan, however, opposed the scheme,⁸⁷ despite its popularity in the colony. He argued that the grant system had been a great evil and allowed the Governor excessive power; that a return to grants on the pretext of providing small farms would only give monopolists an opportunity to buy out and consolidate small-holdings; and that, for all its advantage to the working farmer, it must be rejected on principle as class legislation. Moreover, wary of a Wentworth bearing gifts, he condemned it further as an electioneering move by Wentworth, who knew that the Act of Parliament could not be set aside, and only wished by this manoeuvre to transfer odium from the Council to the Governor, who would have the duty of rejecting a popular but impossible measure.⁸⁸

It has been remarked that the prominence given to the land question by rural romanticists among the radicals [58] of the '40s misdirected the labour movement at a time when the only realistic course was to accept the employment system.⁸⁹ This criticism applies to Duncan and D'Arcy, although it is mitigated somewhat by their concern for the working conditions and wages of both urban and rural employees, their opposition to moves to swamp the labour market, their insistence that the labour force be free and white, and their support for various working-class political actions. D'Arcy, in particular, as editor of a semi-official Catholic journal, was spokesman for—and to—a large group generally disposed to 'have-not' politics. His vehement denunciations of landlordism, industrialism and *laissez-faire* capitalism, though not always entirely relevant to the conditions of the colony, must have appealed to those migrants with memories of Chartism and the Corn Law movement in England and the O'Connellite agitation in Ireland.

Over a period of seven or eight years, the *Chronicle* and the *Register* made a consistent attempt to associate anti-squatter sentiment, working-class interests, and the social and political aspirations of the urban middle class. Although this putative popular front faltered over the squatting question, the persistence with which Duncan and D'Arcy maintained its necessity helped to forge a link between it and the liberalism of a later decade. [59]

They had also helped to forge a tradition of social justice which was a contributing factor in the formation of a radical political tradition among Catholics, and one that was carried on by D'Arcy's successor at the *Chronicle*, E.J. Hawkesley. In his *People's Advocate* and through the Constitutional Association Hawkesley stressed, as Duncan and D'Arcy had done, what must be the theme of our next chapter: the significance of constitutional reform and the sharing of political power. [60]

⁸⁶ Ibid. Wentworth was reflecting the proposals of a public meeting, chaired by Macdermott, held in February 1844. *WR*, 10 February 1844.

⁸⁷ E.g., *Star*, 17 August 1844.

⁸⁸ *WR*, 17 August 1844.

⁸⁹ Hume, 'Working Class Movements', 50.

Chapter III

POLITICS AND THE CONSTITUTION

We have already noted Duncan's conviction that the fundamental division in colonial society was that between an oligarchy and the people. Changing political circumstances meant that the identification of this oligarchy would vary, but in the early years of the *Chronicle* Duncan's main target was the old Anglican elite. He warned that this elite sought to maintain over free men the sway it had held over convicts, and that it aimed, by the exclusion of emancipists and the denigration of working men, to establish its own ascedancy and a 'perpetual distinction of castes'.¹ He found it possible to lay the blame for almost all the colony's ills at the feet of the elite, everything from the incidence of bushranging to the state of education, from religious intolerance to the apathy of the people and the massacres of aborigines.²

The main remedy, Duncan felt at this stage, was the introduction of representative government, for which the colony was now ripe since the abolition of transportation. To give the people a voice in the making of the laws under [61] which they must live was not only a right due to Englishmen, but would lead to a great awakening in New South Wales.³ Archbishop Polding agreed, and wrote anonymously in the *Chronicle* that the appointed Council was 'a mass of dull obstructiveness' unrepresentative of the people and unfit for its purpose, and that it should be replaced with a representative legislature.⁴

It is in this context of opposition to the colonial elite that Duncan's two great campaigns of 1840 must be placed. The first was the agitation against the Masters and Servants Bill, which he considered to have resulted in a victory of 'the people' and of liberal principle over the aristocratic mentality.⁵ The second was the campaign for political equality for emancipists, in which he sought not merely to protect the interests of the emancipist group but, more importantly, to use the influence he had won in the Masters and Servants case to forge a radical alliance of emancipists and immigrants against the colonial 'aristocracy'. In return for delivering immigrant support in the exclusion controversy, Duncan hoped that the emancipists would support the demand for a wide franchise in both the City Council and the anticipated legislature, [62] and so contribute to the development of those representative institutions which he thought would transform the colony.⁶

¹ AC, 2 August 1839 (the first issue); 10 September, 11 and 18 October 1839.

² Respectively, AC 15 September 1840; 3 September 1839; 29 October 1839; 5 November 1839; 17 December 1839.

³ AC, 11 October, 5 November 1839.

⁴ AC, 22 and 26 November 1839. The Mitchell Library holds Duncan's own copies of the *Chronicle*, in which marginal notes indicate Polding's authorship.

⁵ Cf. AC, 1 October 1840, and see above, 40.

⁶ Duncan, *Autobiography*, 38-43.

The failure of the emancipist group to act as Duncan expected was a bitter disappointment to him, but the disappointment was inevitable given his too simple perception of colonial politics. His simple dichotomy had not prepared him for the new alliance that formed in early 1841 as sections of the Patriotic Association, the wealthy emancipists, and the old elite headed by James Macarthur realised the advantage of banding together to secure the advantages of representative government, particularly those which would assure them of cheap land and labour.⁷

At the beginning of 1842 this new alliance petitioned the home government for representative institutions on terms favourable to their own interests. A series of meetings, dominated by Wentworth and Macarthur, manoeuvred to exclude from influence men like Duncan, Macdermott, and McEachern who favoured a wide franchise.⁸ Duncan denounced their 'corruption and bad faith',⁹ but was particularly stung by the involvement of middle-class [63] emancipists in what he called 'an act of the blackest ingratitude ever put on record'. 'Little did I think' he later wrote, 'that these very emancipists... would turn around upon the working immigrants and endeavour to exclude them from the elective franchise, which they themselves owed to the immigrants under my direction'.¹⁰

Duncan's attitude to the wealthy was generally negative, and he considered wealth to be 'the worst of all tests' for the franchise in New South Wales, where wealth was 'for the most part the companion of arrogance and assumption, and often brutality and ignorance'.¹¹ In the colony the aristocratic ideal of *noblesse oblige* had never taken root,¹² and in general the new immigrants were 'superior in intelligence, and in every other respect save wealth, to the bulk of their employers'.¹³ Duncan himself favoured a £10 franchise, in common with most of the other radicals, which he considered would give the vote to all heads of families.¹⁴

During the first half of 1842 Duncan was active in the debate over the incorporation of the City of Sydney, [64] which marked the high point of the political association of radicals and the working class in the '40s.¹⁵ He was a frequent participant in meetings and petitions, urging an adult male franchise and opposing the suggested restrictive qualifications, such as a three-year residence and a £2,000 alderman's qualification.¹⁶ He became an increasingly bitter critic of Wentworth and his fellow 'betrayers' in the Patriotic Association, which he called a selfish landlords' faction,

⁷ Cf. A.C.F. Melbourne, *Early Constitutional Development in Australia: New South Wales 1788–1856; Queensland 1859–1922, with Notes to 1963 by the Editor*, Edited and introduced by R. B. Joyce, Guides to Australian History. (St. Lucia University of Queensland Press, 1963), 259–62.

⁸ Payten, 'William Augustine Duncan', 167–174.

⁹ AC, 1 March 1842.

¹⁰ Duncan, *Autobiography*, 38–39, 42–43. The Wentworth/Macarthur committee proposed a high property qualification which disadvantaged not only working immigrants but urban dwellers in general; AC, 2 April 1842.

¹¹ AC, 5 March 1842.

¹² AC, 31 March 1842.

¹³ Duncan, *Autobiography*, 38.

¹⁴ AC, 31 March 1842.

¹⁵ Hume, 'Working Class Movements', 46.

¹⁶ AC, 7 and 17 May 1842.

prepared to oppose any benefit to the colony, however great, if it cost them money.¹⁷ Duncan had the satisfaction of welcoming both the final Act (which set a £20 franchise, £1,000 alderman's qualification and excluded multiple voting)¹⁸ and the results of the first Council election, which saw 'aristocratic' candidates rejected in favour of merchants and small businessmen, who set and kept the Council on a firmly anti-conservative course.¹⁹

However, it was in some respects a Pyrrhic victory in the war for Duncan's wider program. Wentworth boasted of breaking up Duncan's 'party',²⁰ and though Duncan retorted that he had no party, there was some truth in [65] the jibe. As Margaret Payten notes, he had quarrelled bitterly with James McEachern, and had lost the support of 'a significant portion of the middle class and Catholic emancipist group, whose support was essential for his cause... Duncan had allowed his optimism about the possibility of defeating the 'Colonial Tories' to mislead his judgement about the sectional aims of the wealthy emancipists and others of the middle class. With colossal arrogance he had believed that he could have success in welding together all the non-elite group, in pursuit of the kind of society he himself believed to be morally good'.²¹

These events of 1842 led Duncan to a double disillusion. In the first place, he was now convinced that he lacked ability as an active politician, 'a position for which God and nature, or at all events our individual tastes and habits, have unfitted us'.²² This realisation of weakness was sufficiently temporary, however, for him to discover it afresh three years later.²³ Of more significance was his disappointment with the political judgement of the people, which would in turn diminish his faith in the effectiveness of political institutions to bring about the ideal society. This conservative trend [66] would become more evident as a result of the election campaign for the first partly-elected Legislative Council, which began in late 1842.

Duncan involved himself in the campaign as secretary of the committee of Captain Maurice O'Connell, an Irish Protestant of liberal principles who had attracted broad Catholic support. Many Catholics, however, supported the Wentworth group, of which Duncan was a bitter critic. Wentworth supporters included many 'old' Catholics, including the emancipists Michael Gannon and Roger Murphy, who were both proprietors of the *Chronicle*.²⁴ The major controversy of the campaign, however, and the one that was to prove Duncan's undoing, came not from O'Connell's candidature, but from that of Roger Therry in the seat of Camden. Therry, the Attorney General, was the colony's most prominent and influential Catholic layman, and, though it was not the original basis of his candidacy, he allowed the suggestion to be made that his election would give the 40,000 Catholics of the colony a representative in the legislature. In response Charles Cowper entered the lists with a campaign dedicated to keep-

¹⁷ AC, 30 June 1842; he was referring to municipal rates.

¹⁸ AC, 14 July 1842.

¹⁹ AC 17 November 1842; cf. Roe, *Quest for Authority*, 83–84.

²⁰ AC, 2 July 1842.

²¹ Payten, 'William Augustine Duncan', 182, 184.

²² AC, 2 July 1842.

²³ Duncan, *Autobiography*, 65–66.

²⁴ J.M. O'Brien, 'Catholics and Politics', 102.

ing the Council free of papists.²⁵ The campaign then took on the character of a religious contest, and the sectarianism thus provoked led to the defeat, not of Therry, but of Captain O'Connell and possibly of James Macarthur.²⁶ [67]

Duncan threw the *Chronicle* behind Therry's campaign, not knowing that Therry had received the backing of the Macarthurs, whose influence in Camden was substantial. Duncan, who thought the Macarthurs dishonest, grasping and selfish, and their influence in the colony entirely baneful,²⁷ dismissed rumours of an alliance as attempts to discredit Therry!²⁸ A few days later he had the embarrassment of announcing that the rumours were true,²⁹ though he continued to denounce the arrangement as a betrayal and reduced the *Chronicle's* coverage of the Therry campaign.³⁰ Duncan was thus in the invidious situation of supporting Therry while attacking his most influential supporter.

The conflict was about political strategy: Therry felt—rightly, given the results³¹—that he needed both Catholic and Macarthur support to win; Duncan held, with characteristic intransigence, that a man cannot touch pitch and not be defiled, and that an honourable defeat would be preferable to victory through an 'unprincipled' alliance.³² Now, a man may be admired for preferring principle to political opportunism, but in this case [68] Duncan had let his hostility to the elite lead him into a misjudgement of James Macarthur.³³ As would become apparent in the squatting controversy of the following year, Macarthur's old-world gentry values acted as a moderating influence on the ruthlessness with which the Wentworth coalition pursued its aims,³⁴ and fulfilled, to some extent, the social function which Duncan admired in the English aristocracy. Later he would muse:

Gentlemen of birth and refinement are never so overbearing in their manners and habits, and consequently not so offensive in their political influence, as the bourgeois *gentilshommes*, the upstarts of speedily acquired wealth.³⁵

At any rate, the alliance was not the defilement it was pictured to be: Macarthur thought that Therry would share his own concern for social harmony. The anti-Macarthur campaign to which Duncan contributed served only to leave the moderate-conservative country gentry without its head in the Council.³⁶

In so vigorously opposing both Wentworth and Macarthur, Duncan had heated a furnace so hot for his foes that he was burned himself. He had alienated [69] himself

²⁵ Waldersee, *Catholic Society*, 220–21.

²⁶ *Ibid.*, 221–224. Therry was also opposed on the grounds that he was a Crown servant, e.g., *Colonial Observer*, 11 January 1843.

²⁷ AC, 4 February 1843.

²⁸ AC, 14 January 1843.

²⁹ AC, 16 January 1843.

³⁰ AC, 9 February 1843.

³¹ Waldersee, *Catholic Society*, 221.

³² AC, 9 February 1843.

³³ Waldersee, *Catholic Society*, 55.

³⁴ See, e.g., *WR*, 4 May 1844, where Duncan welcomes the more reasonable tone introduced by Mr Macarthur.

³⁵ *WR*, 28 September 1845.

³⁶ Suttor, *ibid.*

from significant sections of the Catholic population, including Therry, the clergy, and the proprietors of the *Chronicle*, from those who disagreed with his politics, those who saw his intransigence as a liability in the campaign to gain Catholic political representation, and those who merely feared the consequences for the Church if its journal was allowed to be partisan in politics. Therry maintained that the *Chronicle* was 'no longer the organ of Catholics... and that it was now under the entire control of Macdermott'.³⁷ In addition, Duncan had already given offence to the nationalist Irish by his failure to be sufficiently enthusiastic about the visit to Sydney of their hero, Father Therry,³⁸ and by being lukewarm about O'Connell and the Repeal Movement in Ireland.³⁹

Father Murphy, the Vicar General, and in Archbishop Polding's absence the head of the diocese, wrote that Duncan had made the *Chronicle* 'a political firebrand [and] a rock of dissension'.⁴⁰ He recommended to the proprietors [70] that Duncan be dismissed, which was done on 22 February, Archdeacon McEncroe becoming the new editor. The dismissal revealed the political divisions within the Catholic community⁴¹ and McEncroe's editorship continued to do so, his policy being in many respects the opposite of his predecessor's: he welcomed the election of Wentworth and Bland as 'friends of constitutional liberty',⁴² and regretted the defeat of James Macarthur, whom he thought a man of 'high-minded views and liberal principles'.⁴³

The complexity and confusion of the 1843 election make interpretation a difficult task, but one thing which is clear is that there was no 'Catholic vote'.⁴⁴ Even Duncan and McEncroe agreed on this, though one welcomed and the other deplored the fact. McEncroe thought that 'Messrs Wentworth and Bland had as many Irish and Catholic votes as Captain O'Connell'.⁴⁵ Duncan was dismayed at the failure of Catholics to support liberal candidates: [71]

When we see such persons as Farley, Lacey and Galvin on Mr James Macarthur's committee; and not only this, but when find a whole host of Kiernans, and Gormans, and Ryans, and Keighrans, and so forth, calling on Mr Charles Cowper (!) the avowed domi-

³⁷ Diary of Thomas Callaghan, quoted in O'Brien, 'Catholics and Politics', 113-114.

³⁸ O'Brien, *ibid.*, 76.

³⁹ *Ibid.* Duncan thought that a branch of the Repeal Association had been established in Sydney in 1842 with the sole purpose of embarrassing him, because it was known he would oppose it (*Autobiography*, 45). However, this is probably more indicative of Duncan's egocentricity than of the politics of Repeal in Sydney, which gathered little support until O'Connell's arrest in June 1844.

⁴⁰ AC, 23 February 1843.

⁴¹ It is difficult to determine the exact nature of this division. Perhaps it was the same split as the division between the conservative 'respectable' Irish and the Irish working class which is evident in the two Saint Patrick's Day dinners in 1843, one for the Irish establishment and the other for those less well placed; Patrick O'Farrell, *The Catholic Church and Community in Australia: A History* (West Melbourne, Vic.: Thomas Nelson, 1977), 68-69.

⁴² AC, 1 June 1843.

⁴³ AC, 8 July 1843.

⁴⁴ Waldersee, *Catholic Society*, 221-27.

⁴⁵ AC, 20 June 1843.

nant church partisan (!), we must say to ourselves that there is no end to human baseness, perfidy and want of principle!⁴⁶

It is clear that in 1843, as in later elections, Catholics voted according to a range of interests, and would vote even for anti-Catholic candidates (such as Cowper and Lang) if they had policies which pleased them.⁴⁷

What was of significance for Catholic journalism in the colony was the decline of Duncan's faith in democracy, for his disillusion would characterise his new venture, the *Weekly Register*, and would be shared eventually by Michael D'Arcy, McEncroe's successor at the *Chronicle*. 'Why should we spend our days and nights', wrote Duncan,

and waste our constitution in opposing church dominancy and usurped aristocracy, if free and independent electors are too ignorant to distinguish friend from foe, or too venal to vote according to their consciences? Perhaps after all our zeal, it may be but right that such persons should be slaves, and that we are wrong in calling upon them to stand erect like men and enjoy the rights of freemen! We have fought for them, and gained their franchise, and they barter it away for a mess of pottage!⁴⁸ [72]

Soon 'the PEOPLE', the 'real colonists' of 1840,⁴⁹ had become the 'bellowing crowd' of 1844.⁵⁰

Also significant is the fact that Duncan, having failed in his attempt to create a popular alliance against the old elite, now faced a new and more complex opposition entrenched in the very representative legislature in which he had put his hope. Thus he was faced with the need of finding some other safeguard for his vision of the good society. It is from about this time that Duncan begins to argue that in New South Wales the government, and not the leading men, had generally been the champion of political liberality, and may have to protect the colony from its own folly.⁵¹

In the meantime the depression had intervened to complicate the political situation, having the effect, as we have seen, of gathering support among the middle and working classes for the wealthy but financially vulnerable rural interests.⁵² Duncan later theorised that the emancipist agitation 'was about to be succeeded by a violent strife between the elements of aristocracy and democracy, when the monetary crash of 1843-4 interfered and went far to heal all political distinctions'.⁵³ Michael Roe finds this remark puzzling because, like all [73] depressions, that of the 1840s might be expected to have exacerbated class tensions. Duncan was aware of, indeed had participated in, the upsurge of working-class militance, but was disinclined to think in class terms (as were also some of the workers' spokesmen).⁵⁴ He thought rather in terms of conflict of principles, and in blaming the depression for the failure of the hoped for anti-squatting popular alliance, he seems to have been referring to the opportunism of

⁴⁶ AC, 21 January 1843.

⁴⁷ Waldersee, *Catholic Society*, 249-52.

⁴⁸ AC, 21 January 1843.

⁴⁹ AC, 1 October 1840.

⁵⁰ WR, 7 September 1844.

⁵¹ AC, 7 January 1843.

⁵² See *infra* chapter 1.

⁵³ Duncan, 'Notes on Ten Years' Residence', 147.

⁵⁴ Roe, *Quest for Authority*, 92; Hume, 'Working Class Movements', 44-45.

the radical press and the Mutual Protection Association, who justified their support for the squatting regulations by reference to the prevailing economic distress.

Duncan now saw the new Council, dominated by Wentworth and the squatting faction, as the chief threat to his ideal society. Early in 1844, as the squatters' ambitions and strategy became clearer, D'Arcy also joined the attack on the Council. That he could do so and provoke little of the controversy that Duncan had excited in 1843 is perhaps an indication that the perceptions of at least a proportion of his readers had changed.

The main lines of their criticism we have already treated in Chapter I: both Duncan and D'Arcy regarded the Council as little more than a 'squatters' debating club'.⁵⁵ It may be worth reiterating that the basis of their opposition was the conviction that the Council was being used by its members for the aggrandisement of their own class. 'They forget', Duncan wrote, 'that society is composed principally of labourers—they forget that they themselves are now [74] the representatives, not of the few individuals who own the sheep and the lands, but of the community at large'.⁵⁶ Both editors condemned measure after measure of the Council as class legislation: the monetary bills,⁵⁷ its immigration policy,⁵⁸ the Select Committees on Distressed Labourers⁵⁹ and Crown Lands Grievances,⁶⁰ its attitude to transportation⁶¹ and, of course, to the squatting question.

Wentworth was especially reviled, particularly for his continuing attempts to limit the franchise for the Legislative Council and the City of Sydney. His Corporation Bill, which excluded debtors and 'paupers' from the city franchise by requiring the production of a docket for the payment of the previous six months' rent, brought a particularly bitter reaction. Duncan asked how many MLCs would retain their places if they were required to produce a certificate from the mortgagees of their estates for the last six months' interest.⁶² Wentworth, he said, was a man who had betrayed his former principles in order to lead those who have no qualification for authority but the command of money.⁶³ D'Arcy denounced the Bill as a piece of tyranny designed to rob the people first of their [75] birthright, the franchise, and then of their money by taxation without representation.⁶⁴

Duncan used this and similar attempts to narrow the franchise to argue during 1844 that, under the guise of constitutional reform, the squatters aimed to gain permanent possession of political power:

⁵⁵ *MC*, 27 July 1844.

⁵⁶ *WR*, 26 August 1843.

⁵⁷ *WR*, 25 November 1843.

⁵⁸ *WR*, 16 December 1843; *MC*, 30 December 1843.

⁵⁹ *WR*, 28 September 1844.

⁶⁰ *MC*, 31 August 1844.

⁶¹ *MC*, 5 March 1845.

⁶² *WR*, 7 September 1844.

⁶³ *WR*, 28 September 1844.

⁶⁴ *MC*, 7 September 1844.

Their insisting on a high qualification for the elective franchise on the one hand, while they harrass and weaken the government on the other, ought to satisfy every enquiring mind that what they seek is unlimited power for themselves and their class.⁶⁵

Duncan and D'Arcy parted ways, however, over the question of District Councils, a favourite, if not obsessive, concern of the Governor.⁶⁶ To Duncan, the Councils were an indispensable element of the plan for a better society: they would be a civilising influence through centralisation of population; they would provide training in political responsibility, and encourage the growth of schools, public works and religious institutions; and most importantly, by taxing property owners for services rendered, would force the sale of uncultivated land and encourage the growth of small farms.⁶⁷ [76]

When the Legislative Council rejected the District Corporations Bill in July 1844, Duncan over-reacted:

The Council has committed suicide!... An assembly of madmen only could conceive the possibility of carrying on representative government in this colony without municipal institutions... We see no alternative, therefore, but a dissolution of the Council by the Governor, or an annihilation by an Act of Parliament of our sadly abused franchise.⁶⁸

Once again Duncan had let his academic, doctrinaire view of the good society run away with a realistic sense of the possible, for many of the districts were completely unready for municipal institutions.⁶⁹ D'Arcy recognised the reality: in the remote and unsettled districts, Councils were premature and inapplicable, and the project should be postponed for fifty years.⁷⁰

D'Arcy was not insensitive, however, to the importance of political involvement. In fact, he gave the franchise question more extensive and theoretically developed treatment than the disillusioned Duncan. The latter, as we have seen, favoured a £10 franchise, which he thought would give the vote to 'every intelligent and honest householder',⁷¹ but he was anxious to avoid any [77] hint of levelling: 'We should subvert nothing that is established... We acknowledge the rights of birth, the rights of office, and the rights of education and talent'.⁷²

D'Arcy asserted the rights of the people with those flights of rhetoric he reserved for the things about which he felt most strongly. All free men had once had the vote, he told his readers, but had been robbed of their 'sacred primeval birthright, to choose the men who are to make the laws regarding their properties, their liberties and their lives',⁷³ which robbery was the root of all political evils, of blood, tears, deso-

⁶⁵ WR, 28 December 1844.

⁶⁶ K. Grose, 'Sir George Gipps and Municipal Institutions in New South Wales', *Royal Australian Historical Society Journal* 51 (1965): 148–153.

⁶⁷ WR, 20 January 1844.

⁶⁸ WR, 27 July 1844.

⁶⁹ Grose, 'Municipal Institutions', 151.

⁷⁰ MC, 27 July, 27 November 1844.

⁷¹ WR, 5 March 1842.

⁷² WR, 31 March 1842.

⁷³ MC, 18 September 1844.

lation and national debts.⁷⁴ In New South Wales nine-tenths of the people had been sacrificed to the remaining one-tenth, and the operative, ‘the very blood and bone and nerve of society’, had been made a slave: ‘he has no public voice, nor place, nor power to speak for himself. He is sentenced by the men who rule us to political death.’⁷⁵

He was not entirely consistent, however, in proposing a franchise qualification, sometimes urging a £10 rent, and at other times rejecting all property qualifications: [78]

The glorious spark of reason—the impress and image of the Creator himself... gives men dignity, and worth, and value, and desert to possess liberty and natural right; and not the possession of a herd of bullocks, or cows, or sheep... Is a man good because ‘his talk is of bullocks’? Are a few bricks or slabs put together and called a *house*, worth £20 a year, of more value than human arms or limbs or intellects? Away with this legal *brigandage*! Away with our present stunted representation! Give us another and a better!⁷⁶

But for all this D’Arcy is careful to avoid the phrase ‘universal suffrage’, presumably lest he sound like a Chartist, and will later write that society depends most on the middle class, who stand between ‘the encroachments of oligarchical faction on the one hand and the turbulent discontent of a democratic *clique* on the other’.⁷⁷ Though Duncan is more subdued about the franchise, it is he who calls for the formation of a popular anti-squatting party in 1844-45 while D’Arcy was urging that the people avoid ‘unnecessary political agitation’.⁷⁸ Even though D’Arcy continued to support and defend the Mutual Protection Association, for example, and urged the continuance of petitions demanding extension of the franchise, his rhetoric seems to conceal a basic uneasiness about organised working-class political activity, which is not overcome until the threat of renewed transportation convinces him of the need for concerted action.⁷⁹ [79]

This uneasiness on D’Arcy’s part led him to the position to which Duncan had been drawn by disappointment: that is, to a reliance on imperial or gubernatorial authority to protect the radical program from the folly of the colonists. Even before the squatters’ campaign against the depasturing regulations, Duncan had complained of the ‘feeling of incipient disloyalty’ implicit in denigration of the Governor. He noted that most of the advances in the colony—religious and educational establishments, trial by jury, the franchise—had been granted by the government and opposed by the leading colonists. A little embarrassed by the conservative tone of all this, Duncan feels it necessary to say that he is really a radical.⁸⁰

But Duncan’s political radicalism was based on a calculation, namely that representative institutions and an extension of the franchise would serve to advance his social program. When that calculation proved false, it was relatively easy for him to

⁷⁴ MC, 5 October 1844.

⁷⁵ MC, 2 and 13 March 1844.

⁷⁶ MC, 31 July 1844.

⁷⁷ MC, 6 September 1845.

⁷⁸ Ibid.

⁷⁹ MC, 18 September 1844; SC, 28 October 1846; cf. above, 27–28.

⁸⁰ WR, 21 October 1843.

substitute paternalist safeguards for the popular will.⁸¹ ‘What wise or enlightened measures’, he asked, ‘can be expected to result from the sway of the *majority*, unless that majority is enlightened by a proper course of moral and intellectual education?... The government of a despot is the only one fitted for an ignorant people’.⁸²

Such remarks naturally [80] brought the accusation that Duncan was a Government hack,⁸³ but he persevered: though a democrat in principle, he said, the events of 1843-44 had convinced him that the colony was not ready for representative government.⁸⁴ D’Arcy agreed that enlightened governors would be better than a legislature captive to a faction, and that the colony was ‘too new, too crude’ for representative government.⁸⁵

The *Register* was remarkable for its almost complete lack of criticism of the Governor, even though many of his policies, such as those which retained a high land price and discouraged small farms, were anathema to Duncan. He would call on the Governor to act, but never criticise him for not doing so. When other papers reported that Gipps had insulted a working class deputation,⁸⁶ or had been jeered in Hyde Park by a mob which cried out ‘What should we go to our homes for, we’ve got nothing to eat?’⁸⁷ the *Register* refused to notice. The closest Duncan seems to have come to criticism of the Governor was to remark that he held a ‘mistaken opinion’ about the extent of unemployment in Sydney.⁸⁸ [81]

The *Chronicle* was almost as favourable, though D’Arcy allowed himself the occasional criticism, particularly of Gipps’ failure to encourage small farms or to institute an extensive public works program.⁸⁹ For the most part, however, Gipps is praised, even to the extent that D’Arcy recommends him for the rumoured Governor-Generalship.⁹⁰ When Gipps left the colony in 1846 to go away and die of a disease of the heart, he did so to a snub from the Legislative Council and cries of ‘worst Governor we ever had’ from the *Herald* and the *Atlas*.⁹¹ The *Chronicle*, however, was eulogistic,⁹² and apparently reflected Catholic opinion in being so, for the *Atlas* was moved to describe the farewell testimonial presented to the Governor as a ‘catalogue of Papists and Puseyites’.⁹³

Why this should be so is hard to say, for Gipps’ policies had not been particularly favourable to Catholics—for whom he had no special regard⁹⁴—nor to the dreamed of

⁸¹ Payten, ‘William Augustine Duncan’, 197–198.

⁸² *WR*, 27 February 1844.

⁸³ E.g., *WR*, 16 March 1844.

⁸⁴ *WR*, 7 December 1844.

⁸⁵ *MC*, 27 July 1844.

⁸⁶ *Colonial Observer*, 1 June 1844.

⁸⁷ *Sydney Dispatch*, 6 January 1844.

⁸⁸ *WR*, 12 August 1843.

⁸⁹ E.g., *MC*, 13 April, 18 September 1844.

⁹⁰ *MC*, 9 November 1845; cf. 10 August 1844: ‘his statesmanlike firmness’; 23 October 1844: ‘a truly wise and humane man’, etc.

⁹¹ *Sydney Morning Herald*, 3 July 1846; *Atlas*, 11 July 1846.

⁹² *SC*, 15 July 1846.

⁹³ *Atlas*, 11 July 1846. Bishops Polding and Broughton headed the list, which included many prominent Catholic and Anglican clergy and laity.

⁹⁴ Cf. McCullough, ‘Unguarded Comments’, 35, 44.

yeoman society, except in his squatting policy. Perhaps the support for Gipps reflects the same deference [82] to regal authority which moved D'Arcy to hail Queen Victoria as the greatest Sovereign for a thousand years⁹⁵ and to suggest even that 'she would give justice to Ireland if not impeded by a tyrant oligarchy'.⁹⁶ Many Catholics must have felt the necessity of proving their loyalty to Crown and Empire against the calumnies of the Doctor Langs of the world.

For the Catholic community in general, the political events of the early and middle 1840s had brought mixed blessings. The resolution of the emancipist question was an undoubted victory, and one in which Duncan played a significant part. A partial victory was won in the franchise controversy and in the Sydney Council, which continued to be dominated by smaller men among whom were enough Catholics and their sympathisers to win the Council a denunciation as the 'papal-democratic mob'.⁹⁷

However, in another sense, at least in Dr Waldersee's reckoning, those victories had been costly ones, for they were accompanied by a revival of sectarianism and resentment.⁹⁸ And far from this liability being offset by a growth of Catholic solidarity, these years exposed that Irish-Catholic solidarity was largely a myth, and exacerbated the differences between old and new settlers, rich [83] and poor, within the Catholic community, already beginning to be racked also by the conflict between its Irish majority and the English Benedictines.

For Duncan and D'Arcy their involvement in politics in these years was also, on the whole, a disappointing experience, for they had seen the failure of the attempt to create a broad political alliance in support of the new society, and were led to doubt, in their different ways, the value of both a wide franchise and of representative institutions. Their own inadequacies had also been revealed: D'Arcy's inconsistencies poked through his rhetoric, and Duncan proved incapable of making the diplomatic compromise which might have gathered broader support to his campaign. His increasing alienation from the Catholic mainstream is reflected in the declining circulation of the *Chronicle*, which had been second only to the *Herald* at its peak in 1842, a position it lost when Duncan was at his most controversial and which it never regained under D'Arcy's editorship.⁹⁹

But their continuing significance was not political, in the sense that they were able to form a political party, but ideological, in the sense that they had articulated a set of social and political aspirations that appealed to many immigrants and that would be taken up by other men in other years. [84]

⁹⁵ MC, 25 May 1844.

⁹⁶ MC, 21 May 1845.

⁹⁷ *Sentinel*, 12 March 1846; quoted in Roe, *Quest for Authority*, 217.

⁹⁸ Waldersee, *Catholic Society*, 217.

⁹⁹ AC, 10 February 1842; Payten, 'William Augustine Duncan', 209, 222.

Chapter IV

THE ALTERNATIVE SOCIETY: AN ASSESSMENT

It has already been remarked that for Duncan, and to a lesser extent for D'Arcy, the vision of the good society was the final determinant of all opinions: both deplored the kind of opportunism that sacrifices 'great principles to the mere expediency of an hour'.¹ It is necessary now to look at those 'great principles', at the positive aspects of their social program, and attempt a brief assessment.

Both men were aware that the 1840s were a time of momentous change in New South Wales as the influx of free immigrants,² the end of transportation and the beginning of representative government rendered a series of blows to the old penal plantation system of the colony. Both saw themselves as articulating a response to these changes from the point of view of the smaller man, of modest means but honest ambition, who sought a life of prosperity and independence in a new land. Both were convinced that in Australia could be built a new kind of society, free of the evils of the old world, where poor people would not starve in the midst of abundance, nor the fragments of humanity have to watch the rich go by in their splendid carriages.³

Both men deluded themselves into thinking that as the colony was young, it was 'a *tabula rasa*—a blank sheet of paper on which to write our laws, our institutions, our history', and that it could avoid all the errors of the past.⁴ 'Is [Australia] not the nucleus of a great community', D'Arcy declaimed, 'and perhaps, eventually of a mighty empire, the cradle of liberty, the school of wisdom, and lamp of sound political science to all the regions of the east? Are we then to regard ourselves as insignificant?'⁵

Duncan's ambition for his adopted country was correspondingly large. If only men would renounce individual and class interests, he opined, if only they would give up avarice and party spirit, the great work of colonisation might be carried on in a manner worthy of a great nation, and then

poverty and struggling would be succeeded by peace and plenty; ignorance would give place to knowledge; vice to morality; impiety to religion; misery to comparative happiness. By such means only will Australia become what God and nature, in giving her a climate such a man never beheld before, obviously intended her to be—the paradise of the world.⁶

¹ *MC*, 2 March 1844.

² More than 114,000 during the decade; Burroughs, *Britain and Australia*, Appendices 2 and 3.

³ Cf. *MC*, 22 June 1844.

⁴ *MC*, *ibid.*; cf. *WR*, 4 May 1844.

⁵ *MC*, 2 March 1844.

⁶ *WR*, 4 May 1844.

Many of the lineaments of this new society have already emerged in the negative, as we saw in earlier chapters what Duncan and D'Arcy hoped it would *not* be. It would not be a convict society, nor one ruled by an aristocracy, nor one in which a great gulf was set between the rich and the poor; it would not be a land in which [86] immigrants could be exploited by capitalists and speculators, or working men oppressed by those who had studied labour relations amid scourges and fetters; in it men would not be taxed without representation, nor excluded from public life because of the follies of their past, nor have the value of their labour undermined by coolies; it would be no country for 'land sharks and great cormorant speculators', nor for the haughty, nor for those who defraud a man of his wages; it would hold no place for scorners of marriage, religion, the rule of law and all the other benefits of civilisation. It would certainly not correspond with the graziers' ideal of an Australian Arcady, in which a few great squatting lords would ride about Sydney in state while their Gaucho servants roamed after stock through the primeval forest.⁷

Fundamental to the social program espoused in the *Chronicle* and the *Register* was the ideal of 'comfortable independence'⁸ and self-improvement, which was a prominent feature of the immigrant mentality. Independence, in turn, was strongly associated with possession of land and the development of small-scale agriculture.⁹ The independent yeoman farmer was idealised as the foundation of prosperity and virtue for society as a whole, and the base on which might be built a harmonious community of [87] artisans, merchants and small manufacturers, all of them independent, and free of the slavery of the wage system. Duncan summed up his conviction in 1841:

The promotion of agriculture where it is practicable, and of centralisation, by means of the small farm system, is the measure above all others that would conduce to the prosperity and moral advancement of the colony.¹⁰

The arguments advanced in favour of small farms were partly economic, but largely social and moral, couched as they were to appeal to the aspirations of immigrants. On the economic level, it was asserted that small farms would lead to an increase of agricultural production,¹¹ a real enough need for the colony, which was heavily dependent on imported grain.¹²

Michael D'Arcy argued that this situation was a security risk as well as the cause of a drain of capital from the colony.¹³ It was also argued that the development of small scale agriculture would attract immigrants¹⁴ and, in combination with the breaking up of the large estates and fortunes, would stimulate economic growth through the re-distribution of wealth;¹⁵ it was also presented as the solution to the unemployment problem.¹⁶ [88]

⁷ Last sentence, cf. *MC*, 17 April 1844; remainder cf. chapters 1–3.

⁸ *AC*, 16 January 1841.

⁹ Cf. Hume, 'Working Class Movements', 33–35, 40–53; Irving, 'Radical Politics', 14–20.

¹⁰ *AC*, 20 June 1841.

¹¹ *AC*, 20 February 1841.

¹² Wheat acreage in NSW actually declined during the 1840s, from 72,993 acres in 1840 and 76,428 in 1845 to 70,720 in 1850; Michael Roe, '1830–1850', in F.K. Crowley, ed., *A New History of Australia*, Melbourne: Heinemann, 1978, 104.

¹³ *MC*, 10 January 1844.

¹⁴ *AC*, 28 May 1842; *MC*, 2 February 1844.

For the most part, however, the case for small holdings was based on traditionalist moral arguments and on their value as an antidote to the evils said to characterise both British industrialism and the interior under the squatting system.¹⁷ There is ‘more order, more decency, more morality on a farm’, wrote D’Arcy. If only agriculture was widespread, ‘instead of the overflowing deluge of vice we behold... we should have a laughing race... a country studded with farm houses; a sturdy race of farming peasants, subduing the forest, and causing our fields (instead of gum trees) to smile with golden harvests, or blush with the purple vintage’.¹⁸ Agricultural labour is considered not only more satisfying, but more ‘spiritual’ than the dehumanised labour of industry: the soil ‘blesses the humble labours of the husbandman with abundance’,¹⁹ unlike that system ‘that makes operatives work as bullocks, or mill horses, or steam engines, or brute machines:—no, we want that men should go to their work cheerfully as to a pleasant duty, rather than to a tyrant, hopeless task’.²⁰

It is evident that the ideal of the yeoman farmer is, in part, a reaction against industrialisation, and also against the development of investment capitalism. [89] We have already remarked on Duncan’s hostility to ‘ten per cent usurers’. His views on small farms are consistent with that opinion: they represent ‘honest’ industry,²¹ and would be a bulwark against the growth of large-scale enterprise and investment which inevitably leads, in his view, to the centralisation of wealth in the hands of a few and to a general weakening of the economy.²² A society of sturdy, thrifty yeoman farmers would be safe against the kind of ‘monetary tornado’ which hit the colony in the depression years 1841–43, stimulated as it was by greed and wild speculation.²³

Personal possession was also a factor which made a powerful appeal to the immigrant group, many of whom were accustomed to tenantry and insecurity. This was a point much stressed by the Irishman D’Arcy:

Let us have a nation of men who plough THEIR OWN fields, who reap THEIR OWN wheat, who plant and prune THEIR OWN vines, and THEIR OWN fig trees, who shear their OWN sheep, and milk THEIR OWN cows, and make their OWN butter and cheese—these are what we want, and not the centralisation of capital...²⁴

Unlike the squatting system, they said, with its absentee landlords and single shepherds and its concern only for profit, small-scale agriculture based on the family farm would be a civilising influence in a land that would otherwise remain a wilderness. All advantages would flow from it: centralisation of population, education, [90] religion, the rule of law.²⁵ Sturdy peasant patriarchs, reposing like Abraham, Isaac and

¹⁵ *WR*, 20 January 1844; *SC*, 28 October 1846.

¹⁶ *MC*, 6 December 1843.

¹⁷ See above, chapter 1.

¹⁸ *MC*, 17 January 1844.

¹⁹ *AC*, 5 June 1841.

²⁰ *MC*, 28 February 1844.

²¹ *WR*, 17 August 1844.

²² *WR*, 6 January 1844; cf. *MC*, 28 February 1844.

²³ *MC*, 30 October 1844.

²⁴ *MC*, 19 March 1845 (emphasis in original).

²⁵ *WR*, 20 January 1844.

Jacob, each under his own vine, and raising up families of virtuous children, would replace the much-resented moustachioed stockmen, whose lives were full of vice, lawlessness, bad debts and the blood of aborigines.²⁶

... towns and villages will spring up, the face of the desert will be changed, the 'busy hum of men' will be heard where now all is silence and solitude; the howling wilderness will 'blossom like the rose'; and where nature now sits in all her lonely savageness, thousands of contented and cheerful families will be located; the teeming earth will smile with golden harvests, and the praises of God will ascend from the tongues of congregated men in places where now are heard the wild howlings of the native dog... and the awful imprecations of the solitary and half-savage shepherd.²⁷

Concentration, agriculture, population and marriage are watchwords,²⁸ and personal and family residence a *sine qua non* for obtaining land.²⁹

Such idealisation of rural life and of the yeoman farmer had an extraordinary breadth of appeal in the nineteenth century.³⁰ It attracted men as different in their opinions as the Tory Disraeli, the working-class radical Cobbett, and the Chartist Feargus O'Connor. It appealed both to E.G. Wakefield, who saw land management as [91] the means of recreating English society and its class distinctions in Australia, and to his chief critic Samuel Sidney, who saw the country as a potential workers' paradise, where the humbler classes could gain independence and liberty on the land.³¹ And though it is difficult to argue for direct Chartist influence on the writings of D'Arcy and Duncan—O'Connor's Chartist Land Plan, for example, dates only from 1845—they appear at least to have shared common sources and influences: the radicalism of Paine and Spence and the eighteenth-century agrarians, the reaction against industrialism and commercialism, the desire for independence and self-improvement, the backward-looking romanticisation of a rural 'golden age', and, especially for the Irish, the almost mystical quality of the land, which was associated with natural life, happiness and freedom.³²

The small farm ideal was probably also a romanticised picture of D'Arcy's Ireland and Duncan's Scotland. Certainly Duncan reveals his admiration for the egalitarian, agricultural society of his native Aberdeenshire,³³ and he may also have had in mind

²⁶ MC, 20 March 1844; 22 March and 10 May 1845; WR, 20 January 1844.

²⁷ MC, 5 December 1846.

²⁸ MC, 17 April 1844,

²⁹ WR, 18 May 1844.

³⁰ And into the twentieth, especially among Catholics. On the modern Catholic rural movement, see B.A. Santamaria, *The Fight for the Land: The Program and Objectives of the National Catholic Rural Movement* (Melbourne: N.C.R.M., 1942); D.G.M. Jackson, *The Australian Dream* (A.C.T.S., n.d.); Tom Truman, *Catholic Action and Politics*, Rev. ed. (Melbourne: Georgian House, 1960), 32–46.

³¹ F.G. Clarke, *The Land of Contrarities: British Attitudes to the Australian Colonies, 1828–1855* (Carlton, Vic.: Melbourne University Press, 1977), 122–26, 134–38.

³² Cf. David Jones, *Chartism and the Chartists* (London: Allen Lane, 1975), , 60, 128; and Joy McAskill, 'The Chartist Land Plan', in Asa Briggs, ed., *Chartist Studies* (London: Macmillan, 1959), 304–9.

³³ Cf. Payten, 'William Augustine Duncan', 2–5, 104–105.

the tragic consequences of the deprivation of land in the Highland Clearances.³⁴ There may well have been an influence as well from the European Liberal Catholic movement. [93] In Germany, for example, Emmanuel von Ketteler and Karl von Vogelsang were propagating not dissimilar ideas, though in a more explicitly religious context, which opposed capitalism and looked for social models in the (romanticised) corporate rural community of medieval Christendom.³⁵

Duncan developed his rural ideal in semi-Utopian schemes, such as that for communal agricultural settlements modelled on French agricultural orphan schools: he thought that a hundred men with £5 each could form a colony, and publicised the idea in a pamphlet, *An Essay on Self-Supporting Agricultural Working Unions for the Labouring Classes*, which produced some discussion in other papers.³⁶ He believed that the colony could produce olives, vines, rhubarb, even rice and silk in competition with China.³⁷ These schemes were flights of fancy, with little relationship to the realities of the colony. Climate and soil, given the agricultural methods of the time, made three-quarters of the land unsuitable.³⁸ Many small farmers had already failed because of drought, depression, lack of capital or inexperience—and this number included farmers well placed to supply the Melbourne market.³⁹ Many others were severely disadvantaged by the difficulties [94] of transportation and distribution in the colony which, as we have already noted, made imported wheat cheaper than the locally grown.⁴⁰

There were also economic reasons which militated against the successful growth of small-scale farming, principally the lack of a sufficiently large home-market consumption, a situation which would not change until the gold rushes. Contemporary agricultural technology also placed limits on the feasibility of small farms.⁴¹ Lynette Peel remarks that the only real alternative to grazing was a subsistence economy,⁴² though this would probably have been acceptable to Duncan and D'Arcy. The latter commented, in reply to an objection that farming was not profitable, that 'the farmers of Australia must be content to lead, like the farmers of every other country, a frugal, simple and laborious life—this is as it was intended by Providence'.⁴³ However, subsistence farming was hardly possible in an already commercialised economy.⁴⁴

In addition to agriculture, the two editors hoped to see the introduction of wool production on a small scale, and thought, in fact, that the transfer of grazing from large to small establishments would benefit the economy.⁴⁵ At this very time, however, [95] improvements were taking place in the management and technology of

³⁴ John Prebble, *The Highland Clearances* (Harmondsworth: Penguin, 1969).

³⁵ Joseph N. Moody, ed., *Church and Society: Catholic Social and Political Thought and Movements, 1789–1950* (New York: Arts Inc., 1953), 325–583.

³⁶ Payten, *ibid.*, 118–121.

³⁷ *WR*, 30 March 1844.

³⁸ Burroughs, *Britain and Australia, 1831–1855*, 103.

³⁹ Peel, *Rural Industry*, 49, 65–66.

⁴⁰ See above, p. 14.

⁴¹ Peel, *ibid.*, 45–49.

⁴² *Ibid.*, 48.

⁴³ *MC*, 18 November 1843.

⁴⁴ Peel, *ibid.*, 48.

⁴⁵ *WR*, 6 January 1844; *MC*, 28 October 1846.

wool growing which required greater capital investment and the centralisation of resources: increased flock sizes, sheep-washing facilities, fenced paddocks, shearing sheds, presses and other equipment, and, on larger stations, living quarters, carpenters' and blacksmiths' shops, and so on. Many areas, moreover, allowed the grazing of only two hundred sheep or twenty-seven cattle on 640 acres, hardly sufficient to bring prosperity to the yeoman farmer.⁴⁶

There was a tendency, also, to beg the question of whether immigrants wanted to go on the land. No doubt there were many who did, but the real immigration of peasant farmers did not happen until the late 1840's, as a result of the Famine in Ireland. Contemporaries commented on the reluctance of immigrants to go into the interior,⁴⁷ and though in some cases the reason may have been only an unwillingness to be employed under the notoriously bad conditions in the bush, it may also have reflected a preference for urban employment. Not all immigrants shared the yeoman farmer ideal: many chose to accept the employment system.⁴⁸ It should be remembered, too, that many of the unemployed of 1843, whom Duncan and D'Arcy wished to place on farms, were [96] not farmers at all, but skilled artisans.⁴⁹ Even if they were willing to engage in agriculture, their inexperience would probably have led to failure, as it did in the case of poor Pat Malone, who, having failed with sheep, took on cattle, only to be cowed by the bulls of Australia.⁵⁰

The highly doctrinaire nature of Duncan's view of the yeoman society is demonstrated by his rejection of Wentworth's small farm scheme, which had many features in common with his own, but which was based on free grants, a feature which Duncan would not countenance.⁵¹ D'Arcy, however, had no difficulty in accepting the Wentworth scheme.⁵²

Of the two, D'Arcy made the more convincing attempt to spell out a practical policy of land use, attempting to integrate immigration and land policies. He claimed that the wrong type of immigrants were coming out: prostitutes, the scourgings of workhouses, 'pale, half-starved, debilitated weavers and furnace men' who would never become the vigorous peasants and sturdy yeomen on whom future prosperity would depend.⁵³ He realised that immigration policy would powerfully influence the kind of society that was [97] being formed, and resented the use of the colony as a dumping ground for British poor: towards them his characteristic sympathy failed, and for the same reason as he opposed coolies and the revival of transportation—they posed a threat to the ideal society.⁵⁴ Better, he thought, to solve English problems in England by reducing unjust taxes and extending the franchise to create a government that would care for the common people.⁵⁵

⁴⁶ Peel, *ibid.*, 33–38.

⁴⁷ Cf. Burroughs, *Britain and Australia*, 130–132.

⁴⁸ Hume, 'Working-Class Movements', 33.

⁴⁹ Of the 332 on government relief in August 1843, 103 were carpenters, joiners and sawyers; 52 masons; 13 quarrymen; 25 smiths and 139 labourers; Abbott, 'Valparaiso', 6.

⁵⁰ 'Pat Malone', in Manning Clark, ed., *Sources of Australian History* (London: Oxford University Press, 1957), 274–75.

⁵¹ *WR*, 17 August 1844, and see above, [57].

⁵² *MC*, 21 August 1844.

⁵³ *MC*, 28 February 1844.

⁵⁴ *MC*, 1 April, 28 October 1846.

His bias towards an agricultural society is evident in his specific proposals for a land and immigration policy: that land be occupied by the purchaser and his servants to a maximum of 1,280 acres, fit for agriculture; that 'land jobbing, monopoly and centralisation of property be discouraged'; that the minimum price per acre be reduced to five shillings, with seven years to pay; that married immigrants be given a free grant to the value of the passage out, and an additional fifty acres be given to men with six children.⁵⁶ Less doctrinaire than Duncan, however, D'Arcy also gave space to the working conditions that would be desirable for urban workers; he condemned 'sweating' and child labour;⁵⁷ developed a just wage theory, with which we have already dealt;⁵⁸ and castigated employers who demanded of their employees a fourteen- or sixteen-hour day: no one should work more than ten hours [98] a day, and if the wage from ten hours is insufficient for him to live in comfort, then the wage is unjust.⁵⁹

Duncan saw his colonial paradise as still bound to the British nation and government. Indeed, as we have seen, he looked increasingly to the wisdom of the Governor and the 'omnipotence of the imperial parliament' to be the defenders of his hopes against a ruthless and selfish squattocracy.⁶⁰ 'Why break the light cord that binds us to Great Britain' he asked, 'for heavier chains of colonial manufacture?'⁶¹

D'Arcy, however, was ambivalent about independence.⁶² He could not forget that the British were in Ireland as '*exterminators*', that they had shed his people's blood like water for three hundred years to establish tyrant landlords and an exotic Church.⁶³ Yet he thought that Queen Victoria was the greatest sovereign for a thousand years.⁶⁴ A colonial patriot, he derided those who did not care for the future of the colony but only wanted to make a fortune and go 'home' to spend it.⁶⁵ He thought that imperial management of the colonies was universally bad⁶⁶ and that the colony's few posts of honour should be given to sons of the soil, not to English intruders.⁶⁷ In one moment, when the blood stirred, he could say that 'Imagination, as a true prophet, may [99] picture the time when... a people young in strength and aided by the success of revolution, shall throw off their allegiance to Great Britain and proclaim themselves a nation!', and in the next disclaim any disloyal feelings.⁶⁸ Independence may have been the logical conclusion of his flights of imagination, as it was of his hatred of English investment, but he knew that the greater enemies of his hopes were

⁵⁵ *MC*, 12 March 1845.

⁵⁶ *MC*, 12 March 1845.

⁵⁷ *Ibid.*

⁵⁸ See above, [55].

⁵⁹ *MC*, 28 September 1844,

⁶⁰ *WR*, 27 April 1844.

⁶¹ *WR*, 14 December 1844.

⁶² *Ibid.*

⁶³ *MC*, 31 August and 4 September 1844.

⁶⁴ *MC*, 25 May 1844.

⁶⁵ *MC*, 1 March 1845.

⁶⁶ *MC*, 30 April 1845.

⁶⁷ *MC*, 23 August 1845.

⁶⁸ *Ibid.*

in the colony, not in Downing Street, and he felt constrained to look to Sir George Gipps and a committee of English gentlemen to save the colony from itself.⁶⁹

The small farm system was not the only desirable feature of the good society in Australia. The development of education was seen by Duncan as an essential part of the radical program, and like small farms, a necessary condition for civilising the colony. The strength of his convictions about education and the best course for its development was a major contributing factor in his alienation from the Catholic majority, for he was the only Catholic to advocate consistently a national education system, a position he held until the 1880s.⁷⁰ Duncan favoured non-denominational education, in part because he was convinced that a denominational system, requiring three or four school masters in every small village, would never work in the thinly-peopled colony.⁷¹ But he also believed that a general [100] system was preferable to a denominational one in a pluralist society such as Australia, because it would help to heal unnecessary animosities between Christians.⁷² He rejected the criticism that mixed schools would encourage religious indifferentism, and the *Chronicle's* charge that it would be an opening to 'atheism and pantheism', as the 'fears of weak minds'.⁷³

Duncan, a teacher himself, had a generous faith in the power of education, which may have been shared by Archbishop Polding, but does not seem to have been by the Irish majority. D'Arcy announced that devout ignorance was infinitely preferable to knowledgeable impiety, and that education ought to be suited to the station in life of the recipient, for it is of no use 'to a milkmaid to be a poetess, nor to a blacksmith to understand logarithms'.⁷⁴

Duncan, on the contrary, thought that no transformation was beyond the power of education: if only the children of the humbler classes were given a good moral education, he declared, 'we should not see boys clambering up behind coaches, adding to the toil of hard-working animals... they would not rob the nests of poor birds... they would not tie cans to dog's tails... they would not throw orange [101] peel on the pavement... they would not knock at people's doors and run away'.⁷⁵

The debate on the education question, which affected Catholics as a religious as well as a socio-economic group, raged throughout the second half of 1844 and raised important questions about the nature of colonial society and the place of Catholics and their Church in it. As a man sympathetic to Liberal Catholicism, Duncan looked on secular culture with optimism; he saw no reason to think that religion and science were opposed,⁷⁶ or that Australian Catholicism ought to be identified with the Irish

⁶⁹ MC, 5 July 1845

⁷⁰ Payten, 'William Augustine Duncan', 141.

⁷¹ WR, 6 July 1844.

⁷² WR, 30 August 1839.

⁷³ WR, 6 and 13 July 1844; MC 18 September 1844. J.H. Plunkett and Roger Therry also supported national education; the clergy entirely opposed it. O'Brien, 'Catholics and Politics', 174-175.

⁷⁴ MC, 20 July 1844.

⁷⁵ WR, 4 May 1844.

⁷⁶ Payten, 'William Augustine Duncan', 307-320.

Church and Irish nationalism.⁷⁷

D'Arcy, on the other hand, attempted to confuse Irish and local issues by claiming that the national education system was born of 'the same anti-Irish spirit which enacted the hell-born penal code... the ejection acts... the police act... which now fills Ireland with troops ready to shed the blood of its people rather than render justice...'.⁷⁸

Duncan was appalled at D'Arcy's rejection of his hopes for the integration of Catholics into New South Wales society.⁷⁹ As he had once condemned Anglican attempts to gain control of education,⁸⁰ he now deplored [102] the entry of the Catholic clergy into the education debate:

We cannot but exclaim against the indecency of a clergyman [Father McEncroe] disgracing his sacred profession by parading the public stage as the avowed leader of a bellowing crowd... In conduct like this there is neither Catholicism nor Christianity of any kind, but even from this most deplorable affair may be drawn a powerful argument for a general system of education... Unquestionably, in a country where a general system of education is in operation, no clergyman could thus control the popular will in respect of a political question, and God forbid that such exhibitions should be repeated among us... Let the sanctuary be sacred against the intrusions of laymen, but let clergymen either absent themselves from the political arena, or if they claim their rights as citizens, let them exercise them simply as individuals, without abusing their sacred influence to control public assemblies.⁸¹

The issue in this matter was not only clerical participation in politics, but the matter of forming the new society, free of the rancours of the old. Duncan was one of those who espoused a sort of 'anti-sectarianism', by which religion was held to be personal rather than communal, and so able to be virtually excluded from public life.⁸²

However, the revival of sectarianism which accompanied the influx of Irish migrants during 1838-1841, the activities of Doctor Lang and other bigots, and the 1843 [103] election campaign renewed the Catholic sense of persecution and insecurity, and virtually guaranteed the aggressive Irishism which Duncan deplored.

In many ways the 'alternative society' which D'Arcy and Duncan attempted to conjure up in their journals was not unique to them. Many of their policies were conventional.⁸³ Each believed that his program was a response to the conditions of the colony and the challenge of making a new society in the Antipodes, a response both to

⁷⁷ 'Our religion is neither English nor Irish, but Catholic', he would write in 1857, 'and our patriotism, if we hold our place here, must be neither the one nor the other, but Australian'; quoted in Suttor, *Hierarchy and Democracy*, 57.

⁷⁸ MC, 14 September 1844.

⁷⁹ WR, 7 September 1844.

⁸⁰ WR, 13 August, 8 October 1839.

⁸¹ WR, 7 September 1844. Duncan was later prominent in the campaign to assert the right of lay participation in church government; Suttor, *Hierarchy and Democracy*, *passim*.

⁸² A.W. Martin, 'Henry Parkes and the Political Manipulation of Sectarianism', *Journal of Religious History* 9 (1976); 86.

⁸³ Cf., e.g., *Guardian*, 27 July 1844, and *Star*, 4 May 1844 on small farms.

the desires of immigrants and the call of hundreds of millions of acres ready 'for the axe, the spade, the plough and the pruning hook'.⁸⁴

However as Margaret Payten remarks, the radical program was not a response to a new situation. In fact, it rejected pastoralism, the unique economic feature of the colony and the chief stimulus to its growth, and based its political analysis on the transposition of colonial landowners and the European aristocracy. It was rather a moral statement about the good life based on *a priori* assumptions. 'It was conservative and traditional where it most pretended to be radical and new'.⁸⁵ [104]

⁸⁴ MC, 21 August 1844.

⁸⁵ Payten, 'William Augustine Duncan', 152–154.

CONCLUSION

In many ways, then, Duncan and D'Arcy had failed. Their dream of yeoman farmers subduing and peopling the wilds was fanciful in the conditions of the 1840s. They had been unable to rally Catholics as a body to their radical cause, or to mould an anti-squatter popular alliance. It came to appear that their position was a conservative one, opposed to colonial self-government and inhibiting the return of prosperity. Some would say that they merely distracted men from the real concerns of colonial history.⁸⁶

However, that seems to me an ungenerous judgement. Among their achievements must be numbered their defence of the right of working men to employment and to participation in political life; their fight against the various threats posed to the value of labour; their perseverance in the early stages of what would prove a lengthy struggle against pastoral monopoly of the land, and their perspicacity in seeing the consequences of a squatter victory against the regulations of 1844. Dr Gollan is mistaken in saying that 'fears of the pastoralists' monopolistic intentions did not become articulate until after 1847',⁸⁷ as we have seen throughout this thesis. D'Arcy and Duncan made a consistent attempt to associate [105] the interests of working men with the social and political aspirations of the rising urban middle class in an anti-squatter alliance, and that this attempt was not entirely an historical dead end is seen in the links between their program and that of the liberalism of the 1850s.⁸⁸

And in another sense, I believe, they had glory by a losing day. Much of their social program, it is true, was fanciful and Utopian. But if we accept that Utopia is 'the motor of intellectual history'⁸⁹ we can see that even failure does not rob them of all achievement, for they gave to the dreamers of dreams an imaginative symbol of their hopes, and thereby the encouragement to work for further reforms. [106]

⁸⁶ E.g., Hume, 'Working-Class Movements', 50.

⁸⁷ *Radical Politics*, 5.

⁸⁸ Cf. Irving, 'Radical Politics', 20–21.

⁸⁹ J.C. Davis, 'Utopia and History', *Historical Studies* 13 (1967): 165–167.

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